

INTERPERSONAL SUPPORT, EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE AND SELF-EFFICACY: A CAUSAL MODEL ON SELF-CONCEPT OF PUBLIC SCHOOL TEACHERS

¹Antonio Palma Gil L., ²Eugenio S. Guhao, Jr. S., (MD)

^{1,2}Department of Education

^{1,2}University of Mindanao

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11654951>

Published Date: 14-June-2024

Abstract: The study focused on a model for the self-concept of teachers based on the relationships between interpersonal support, emotional intelligence, and self-efficacy. The objective was to understand how these variables interact to influence the self-concept of teachers. The study involved 1000 secondary public school teachers from different schools in Region XI, Philippines using Structural Equation Modelling (SEM). Findings showed significant correlations between the endogenous variable, self-concept, and the following exogenous variables namely: interpersonal support, emotional intelligence, and self-efficacy. Further, Model 3 was the best-fit structural model in which all exogenous variables had a direct influence on the endogenous variable, self-concept. Through a series of structural modifications, Model 3 revealed that self-concept was defined by its three retained indicators namely: competence, acceptance of risk, and initiatives while the two retained indicators measured interpersonal support namely: principals and co-teachers. Emotional intelligence was described by its two remaining domains: self-regulation, and social skills. On the other hand, self-efficacy was assessed by its two retained elements, namely: managing students' content and instructional practices and support. The findings of this study imply teachers adequate interpersonal support by providing them training on emotional intelligence and self-efficacy.

Keywords: educational management, secondary public-school teachers, interpersonal support, emotional intelligence, self-efficacy, self-concept, SEM, Region XI, Philippines.

1. INTRODUCTION

Teachers play a pivotal role in shaping the future of societies worldwide. Their influence extends far beyond the confines of the classroom, impacting not only the academic development of students but also their personal growth and societal contributions. A teacher's efficacy in the classroom is shaped by a complex interplay of intrapersonal and external factors. Specifically, their self-concept, encompassing their perception of themselves and their behavior, serves as a foundational cornerstone of their teaching practice (Maksimovic & Osmanovic, 2019; Ferreira et al., 2020). This theory is deemed significant as to its indirect impact on the students' academic performance and achievement.

A teacher's self-concept is further shaped by numerous factors, including interpersonal relationships, emotional intelligence, and self-efficacy (Miller, 2020; Lumbantobing, 2020; Gilar-Corbi et al., 2019). Interpersonal relationships influence how teachers perceive themselves, a concept elucidated by symbolic interactionism. According to this theory, social interactions and feedback significantly impact teachers' self-esteem and self-concept (Deng et al., 2020; Mateo 2019; Sumiran et al., 2022; Amril et al., 2023). Furthermore, while no direct relationship exists between emotional intelligence and self-concept, there is evidence to suggest that emotionally intelligent teachers tend to have positive self-concepts. They demonstrate proficiency in monitoring, understanding, and regulating their own emotions (Yang, 2022). Additionally, self-efficacy plays

a crucial role as teachers often evaluate their self-concept based on their perceived professional effectiveness. These factors are essential domains to consider when examining teachers' self-concept (Saloviita & Pakarinen, 2021).

However, there is an existing struggle with teachers' self-concept as compounded by various social issues, that in turn impact their effectiveness. Challenging students often exhibit disrespect and lack of empathy towards teachers and peers (Amstad & Muller, 2020; Kollerova et al., 2023). Additionally, when students' learning is poor, teachers may perceive their role negatively. In the Philippines, teachers face heavy workloads and low salaries, worsened by an experimental curriculum that frustrates both educators and students (Act Forum Online, 2023; Mateo, 2019). These conditions bring stress, diminishing teachers' job satisfaction, commitment, self-efficacy, and self-concept, thereby increasing the risk of burnout (Jomuad et al., 2021; Masoom, 2021).

There have been numerous studies that looked at the specific impacts of the interpersonal relationship, emotional intelligence, and self-efficacy. Miller (2020) significantly linked teachers' interpersonal relationships to their self-concepts. These self-concepts are molded by environmental interactions, shaping how teachers engage with students, parents, and others. Similarly, Lumbantobing (2020) found that emotional intelligence directly impacts self-concept. Improving both self-concept and emotional intelligence can enhance teachers' lives, fostering productivity and fulfillment. Gilar-Corbi et al. (2019) suggests fostering emotional intelligence through self-understanding, effective communication, and stress management. Thus, factors like self-efficacy, emotional intelligence, and external influences are crucial for maintaining teachers' self-concept.

This study was conducted to explore a structured model of interpersonal support, emotional intelligence, and self-efficacy in the self-concept of teachers. This includes other related studies that will serve as the basis for this study. This study presents an independent variable, namely interpersonal support, with indicators, namely, parents, government, principal, and co-teachers. The next independent variable is emotional intelligence, with indicators namely self-regulation, self-awareness, social skills, empathy, and motivation. The last independent variable is self-efficacy, with indicators namely, time, facilities, and resources; community support and involvement; managing students' content; teacher's leadership; school leadership; professional development; and instructional practices and support. On the other hand, the dependent variable indicated as self-concept also has indicators, namely, competence, interpersonal perception, acceptance of risk and initiatives, relationship with students, satisfaction, and self-acceptance.

Interpersonal support to teachers, provided by peers, teachers, parents, and the government is crucial for achieving positive and effective educational goals of students. Specifically, parents are the vital partners of teachers in improving academic performance of students (Deng et al., 2020). Both home and school environments contribute to crafting Individualized Educational Programs (IEPs) tailored to each student's needs, emphasizing the importance of parent-teacher collaboration (Ahn & Myoungsuk, 2020; Van Der Wal, 2020). Furthermore, higher levels of parent trust in teachers positively influence parental educational involvement, leading to improved student outcomes (Vanner et al., 2022). Enhanced parent trust in school correlates with reduced reports of student emotional symptoms and behavioral difficulties, highlighting the importance of school-based interventions for students and families. Ultimately, student success reflects the combined efforts of teachers and parents, underscoring the pivotal role of both parties in fostering academic achievement (Vanner et al., 2022).

Teachers require increased support from the government to address various challenges within the education system. Mateo (2019) highlights the need for governmental assistance, especially as teaching roles have become more complex and demanding while teacher compensation has declined relative to other professions. Factors contributing to the teacher shortage include low payments and inadequate financial incentives such as diversified pay and loan forgiveness (Worth et al., 2022). Insufficient salaries often lead teachers to consider alternative career paths, particularly in industries where math or science expertise is more lucrative (Thurmond, 2023). Addressing underpayment issues is crucial, as public-school teachers often face financial burdens related to teaching materials and personal expenses (Mampo et al., 2022; Litvinov, 2020). In the Philippines, the Department of Education (DepEd) is addressing the shortage of full-time and substitute teachers, although financial constraints remain a challenge. Additionally, government policies play a significant role in determining job satisfaction among teachers, with self-awareness positively correlated with job satisfaction (Aznan et al., 2019; Supramaniam & Singaravelloo, 2020). The government must address teacher workloads, provide incentives, and acknowledge educators' achievements to improve overall efficacy and job satisfaction within the teaching profession.

A supportive principal enhances teacher effectiveness by prioritizing ongoing, collaborative support (Meador, 2019). This involves valuing efforts to monitor teacher effectiveness, fostering trust, and providing clear objectives and decision-making powers (Sumiran et al., 2022; Amril et al., 2023). Principals' instructional leadership positively influences teachers' self-efficacy, strengthening their belief in their ability to engage students and manage classrooms (Winn et al., 2021; Siriparp et al., 2022; Özdemir et al., 2020). Additionally, principals who demonstrate effective instructional leadership behaviors contribute to increased collective efficacy among teachers (Karaköse et al., 2024). Schools with principals promoting shared instructional leadership experience higher rates of teacher collaboration and student achievement. Courageous instructional leadership and support for teacher collaboration lead to improved student outcomes, emphasizing the importance of principals fostering collaborative practices and openness to new teaching strategies (Nwukor, 2023).

Teachers benefit greatly from collaboration with their peers, as seeking help from other professionals or co-teachers offers effective solutions to teaching challenges. According to the Global State of Digital Learning Survey, over 30% of teachers and nearly 50% of administrators prioritize teacher collaboration (De Jong et al., 2019). Collaborative efforts allow teachers to share concepts, ideas, and experiences, enhancing academic rigor and student learning outcomes through creative lesson planning and instructional strategies (Davis, 2019). Moreover, relationships with colleagues serve as a buffer against burnout, fostering feelings of solidarity and empathy (Van Droogenbroeck et al., 2021). Teacher commitment is influenced not only by relationships within the school but also by the support received from local educational authorities (Atmaca, 2022; Shu, 2022). Sensitivity to factors enhancing teacher commitment, including school climate and interpersonal relationships, is crucial for promoting school goals and academic achievement (Manla, 2021). Open communication among colleagues fosters confidence and mutual support, ultimately improving teacher commitment and school performance (Chiriac et al., 2023).

Emotional intelligence is the aspect of human intelligence that governs our ability to know, understand, manage, and use emotions as a solution to solving problems of a personal and interpersonal nature (Yang, 2022). A teacher with high emotional intelligence builds an empathic environment and a high ability to motivate and encourage students, which lead to a path of excellent indirect personality development that creates pleasure in learning. In fact, emotional intelligence is even more influential when it comes to predicting teacher effectiveness and students' learning (Abiodullah, et al., 2020; Verma, 2023). This skill helps them guide students and interact effectively, which leads to productive learning outcomes (Cherry, 2019).

Emotional intelligence impact self-concept of teachers through self-regulation, self-awareness, empathy, motivation and social skills. Teachers with high EI are more likely to have a positive and resilient self-concept. In turn, teachers can maintain a calm and supporting learning atmosphere, conducive for the students' learning (Monteiro et al., 2021; Schunk et al., 2022). The first component, self-regulation, refers to the management of thoughts, behaviors, and emotions (Schunk et al., 2022). Based on a study in 2013, Iranian EFL teachers who demonstrate high levels of self-regulation tend to be more self-efficacious in their professional practice. This agreed with a more recent study showing that emotional competence and personal values drive a teacher's motivation and self-efficacy (Barni et al., 2019)

The second component, self-awareness, is the ability to recognize feelings and manage emotions (Vanner et al., 2021; Su et al., 2022). As for teachers, being aware at work can promote a good climate within the school premises. Teachers must adopt enabling wellbeing strategies if they are to be retained as effective practitioners and as role models that contribute to the wellbeing of future generations. The third component is social skills. Teachers that build positive relationships and effectively managing social situations can boost self-esteem and reinforce a positive self-concept. Furthermore, students learn more from teachers who have good interaction or communication skills (Obelot, 2020). This implies that teaching does not only depend on the knowledge of the teacher but also on the method and style of the teacher's communication skills (Sword, 2024). Empathy, the fourth component, involves understanding students' personal and social situations, caring for their emotions, and responding compassionately while maintaining focus on their learning (Meyers et al., 2019). By empathizing, teachers can effectively reach out to students, fostering a positive learning environment where students feel comfortable sharing ideas (Vanner et al., 2022; Zhou, 2022).

The last component of emotional intelligence is motivation, especially crucial for teachers. A teacher's motivation is reflected in the outcomes of their students' learning efforts, highlighting its importance in driving educational success (Fuertes et al., 2023). A 2017 study conducted in Pakistan highlighted the impact of emotional intelligence on teachers' performance, revealing that teachers who possess effective physical and mental skills and sustain self-motivation tend to demonstrate better teaching performance. Similarly, research by Lavy (2022) underscores the positive correlation between a sense of meaning at work, motivation, and teaching performance.

A study by Skaalvik & Skaalvik (2019) indicated that teacher self-efficacy and collective teacher efficacy should be conceptualized as different but correlated constructs. Although teacher self-efficacy and collective teacher efficacy were positively correlated, these constructs were differently related to the school context. Teacher self-efficacy was most strongly related to teachers' relations with parents. Positive relations with the parents of their students predicted that teachers had stronger self-efficacy beliefs. Classroom environment was measured through global ratings of positive classroom climate, productive use of instructional time, and teacher evaluative feedback. Positive classroom climate reflected pleasant conversations, laughter, and enthusiasm; productive use of instructional time reflected efficient transitions among different activities and consistent provision of appropriate activities and pacing (Amerstorfer & Von Münster-Kistner, 2021).

It is indicated that care needs to be given to teachers as they develop efficiency in using innovations such as new school facilities. Suggestions include giving teachers time to develop personal comfort with and ownership over the technological intervention and providing teachers with models of successful implementation as well as just-in-time support (Munna & Kalam, 2021). In addition, the increasing demands on teachers' intellectual and emotional resources are linked to increased occupational stress, burnout, and decreased job satisfaction (Agyapong et al., 2022). Thus, proper time management by teachers in their job might increase the efficiency of their teaching pedagogy, but it will also lessen their stress and allow them to easily complete heavy workloads.

The findings on overall trends in the allocation of classroom time are troubling. The findings in 2013 on science time in elementary classrooms, together with the long record of prior research on the importance of adequate instructional time, point to the conclusion that advancing student interest in pursuing studies in science and related fields may be difficult. Lack of adequate time for instruction in elementary grades is likely to decrease the chances of closing the achievement gap in later grades for students from low-income families. This agrees with a more recent study that instructional time is indeed important to maximize student learning (Wedel, 2021). Therefore, sufficient instructional time for teachers is badly needed in order to foster the knowledge of students. In the present study, classroom processes such as quality of instruction were measured through students' questionnaires. In primary school classes, significant correlations were found between time spent by teachers and classroom sizes. Specifically, students in smaller classes perceived higher teaching quality, like less pressurized teaching, more student participation, and higher explaining time expenditure. This explains that teachers' time in the classroom does affect the academic performance of their students because the more time they spend teaching, the more they get interested in and involved in the class discussion (Laitsch et al., 2021).

In addition, research finding as regards the factors encouraging school facility depreciation showed that excess pressure on the available facilities, lack of proper maintenance, delayed maintenance, over centralization of maintenance, and environmental pollution (Hassanain et al., 2019). This conveys that the lack of facilities at a school may affect its reputation and the overall performance of the institution. The availability of learning spaces other than classrooms is needed to foster and reinforce the teaching and learning experience. Lack of gymnasiums or sports grounds, labs, libraries, and music and computer rooms might put the school at a disadvantage. These serve as spaces where students and teachers mutually practice sports, engage in physical activity or play, listen to music and practice musical instruments, experiment and rehearse, and have access to unique and diverse information through books or technology networks (Mirana, 2022).

Furthermore, the school environment plays a crucial role in the experience of satisfaction among public school teachers (Masoom, 2021b). When the school environment is considered, it suggests that a positive environment with sufficient learning materials and resources such as internet access, printers, and computers decrease teacher dissatisfaction, thus, teachers who perceive a more positive environment and have more control over their classrooms are more satisfied with their jobs. Furthermore, e-mail, e-books, and e-journals are the most frequently used internet facilities by academic staff, they also use the same internet facilities for their teaching and research purposes. Relevance of information is among the reasons advanced for the use of such internet facilities. Having various technological tools, such as e-mail and adequate internet speed, is crucial to the self-efficacy of educators (Usman & Madudili, 2019; Timotheou et al., 2022).

Disruptive student behavior in the classroom is a major concern in school systems today. Students in classrooms with frequent disruptive behavior experience less academic engagement and lower academic outcomes (Gallegos et al., 2019). The lack of effective classroom management may also worsen the progression of aggressive behavior for children in classrooms. A correct approach to the students is needed for a teacher to practice avoiding the commotion and aggressive behaviors of students. Supportive leadership was found to be utilized in encouraging the teachers to work as well as in their personal lives. Therefore, school administrators should be friendly to their teachers by praising and encouraging them, especially on important occasions. They must be merciful, kind, and understand teachers' feelings. This conveys that the

school administrators and teacher's relationship must be at its peak, thus affecting the overall content of the classroom (Franklin & Harrington, 2019).

Moreover, educational administrators are rarely supermen, but they do acquire and represent a wide range of experience. In teacher education, the school head, such as the principal, is regarded as the educational administrator in the secondary school system, and he is the key person in the administrative organization together with the school administrators. It is their duty to oversee the proper running of the school in terms of staff and students' welfare, the development and implementation of educational programs, and the manifesting of policies and regulations for the betterment of their institution (Ray et al., 2021).

Communication practices categorize the strategies as part of instructional practices that participants used to form teacher-student connections that established a foundation for engaging and motivating students' interaction with the course content (Vanner et al., 2022). To compensate for the lack of visual reinforcement inherent in face-to-face instructional settings, participants used clear, concise writing techniques, expressed care and concern, and demonstrated an interest in the students' worlds to initiate relationships with them. In addition, a study finding suggests that mastery-oriented instructional practices in a lecture are more closely associated with features of teacher motivation that involve a caring attitude and an interest in students' personal characteristics and development. Mastery-oriented practices involve encouraging students to master learning tasks by attributing their achievement to effort, focusing on their individual progress, and adapting tasks to their interests and abilities (Hettinger et al., 2023).

An analysis also shows that teacher leadership is strongly related to student achievement. The results clearly show that teacher leadership and the amount of teacher influence in school decision-making are independently and significantly related to student achievement after controlling for the background characteristics of schools (Shen et al., 2020). Studies also suggest that leadership matters and that good school leadership actively involves teachers in decision-making, and that these are tied to higher student achievement. Teacher leadership implies that it is the job of all teachers to engage fully in fueling the forward movement toward improving learning for students. Through teachers' collective work, they learn how interdependent they are and thus work harder to be effective as a collective. Without realizing it at first, they act with the notion that together they are stronger, thus enhancing their decision-making skills with their colleagues (Warren, 2021; Woo et al., 2022).

Novice teachers can develop their leadership capacity through principal-delegated and/or self-initiated professional development opportunities (Koty, 2020). In this respect, teacher leadership development can be incubated and developed through the interplay of teachers' awareness, willingness, and self-initiation, as well as principals' delegation, facilitation, and identification of potential leadership talents. Moreover, a study revealed that teachers' perception of cooperation at the level of the leadership team is directly related to teachers' organizational commitment. It was claimed that increments in organizational outcomes are associated with the extent to which the leadership team shares information, collaborates, and makes decisions together as a group (Lenarz, 2020).

Moreover, courses and workshops may be quite useful in the learning processes of teachers, while learning in one's own school practice may have another function (Munna and Kalam, 2021). Not all the forms of activity that facilitate teachers' learning will necessarily be relevant for all teachers. The professional development of teachers needs some time and the help of colleagues to improve their teaching practices. Teacher development is also a way of searching for unifying threads in the midst of diversity. Cognitive theory and research have helped unveil some of the constant factors, such as the role of prior beliefs and perceptions of self-efficacy as individual factors supporting or hindering change, while socio-cultural theory has directed attention to the external situations that likewise affect change in teaching practices (Bergmark, 2020).

Professional development is an important strategy for ensuring that educators are equipped to support deep and complex student learning in their classrooms (Ventista & Brown, 2023). Also, professional development might be composed of content-focused practitioners who incorporate active learning strategies and work in collaboration with students and colleagues to provide coaching and expert support, including time for feedback and reflection. Ensuring that professional development improves student learning begins by incorporating identified features of effective learning into teacher professional development. District leaders must then ensure that they use appropriate tools to evaluate teachers' experience, learning, and instruction so that they can continue to refine the professional development they offer for teachers. The final test of the effectiveness of professional development is whether it has led to improved student learning (Sims et al., 2021).

In addition, the aforementioned findings are also important for policymakers and practitioners since the results provide evidence that school contexts need support in developing instructional time. They also suggest a focus on collaborative

work to decide about school improvement actions and then to put those into effect by focusing on improving teacher instruction and the environment surrounding instruction through varied practices (Qin, 2022). The development of such a library of lessons would provide a rich resource for the improvement of teacher practice, thereby affording equitable access to clear college and workforce readiness expectations for all. Externally developed, research-based, and standards-aligned examples of instruction would be very beneficial, especially for those teachers who need them the most. Trained professional development providers might help schools translate such lessons and work to align local instructional efforts to the college and career readiness standards (Sims et al., 2021).

Self-concept in teachers can be defined as self-perceptions of one's own teaching effectiveness. Accordingly, the importance of competence belief, sometimes labeled as self-efficacy or self-concept, influences the psychological variables of a teacher (Orakçı et al., 2023; S. Li, 2023). Wigfield (2000) and Eccles expectancy-value theory (1983) denotes that a teacher's worth views of working together with a positive competence belief could effectively affect the actual teaching behaviors and teacher's beliefs. According to Mitchell (2019), self-concept revolves around the self-perspective competence of a teacher, specifically in terms of their efficacy in classroom management, instruction, and etc. In Barni et al. (2019), teachers who were high in competence beliefs in their teaching influenced the students' learning positively.

It is important to design a training program that could contribute to the improvement of teachers' empathy and their positive self-image (Aldrup et al., 2022). The program should be based on participation in social activities, keeping in mind that the teaching profession includes communication among students, teachers, and other social representatives. A positive self-concept would support teachers' empathic capacities and competence while executing a lecture, and vice versa. The most important implication is that in this way, it is possible to improve the quality of teaching and education in general. Moreover, it is important to consider teachers' self-concepts and their value beliefs to facilitate student learning. These findings will improve understanding of the teaching process and have important implications for teacher education programs. Given teacher self-concepts and the value of learning, this significantly increases the efficiency and productivity of a teacher in a class (Barni et al., 2019; Martinsone & Žydzūnaitė, 2023).

Based on a study, educational activity is a process of constant creativity. But unlike the creativity in other fields (science, technology, and art), the work of the teacher is not intended to create something socially valuable and original because it is always the product of the personal development of the teacher. It is caused by the creative potential of the personality, which is based on the accumulated experience of their social, psychological, pedagogical, and specific knowledge, new ideas, and abilities (Kutsak et al., 2023). Thus, it enhances overall competence. Pedagogical competence is primarily concerned with the level of understanding of learners, instructional design, and implementation of learning. The diagnosis, evaluation, and development of learners have received significant support in the form of professional pedagogical teaching. Thanks to the support, it was found that the pedagogical impact on improving the performance of learning is primarily concerned with the mastery of teaching materials, the ability to manage learning, and a commitment to doing a good job (Mahmud et al., 2019; Munna & Kalam, 2021).

The quality of the interpersonal relationship between teachers and students was significantly related to teachers' emotional experiences and communication during instruction. Closeness, reflecting the positive interpersonal relationship between students and teachers, was particularly important for teachers' experiences of joy in the classroom but was also a significant predictor of teachers' anger and anxiety (Xie & Derakhshan, 2021). Teachers who felt connected with their students were more likely to report joy and less frequently reported anxiety and anger. Furthermore, a study in 2014 assessed the impact of four interpersonal relationships (students, colleagues, supervisors, and parents) and teaching-related and non-teaching-related workload on burnout among senior teachers. Burnout among senior teachers deserves special attention; it was indicated that burnout is related to attrition and the early retirement of teachers. Preserving positive interpersonal perception among colleagues is a must to avoid early exit in the field. Similarly, a more recent study has shown that maintaining positive interpersonal among colleagues can buffer stress of teachers (Pyhältö et al., 2020).

Positive relationships with colleagues are a key factor in enabling teachers to manage challenges and professional development. Feeling supported by individuals in the wider system who were "credible" that the teachers could "trust" with a shared vision of the change process emerged as a critical factor in helping the teachers continue to implement change even in the face of seemingly insurmountable systemic blockages (Akinyemi et al., 2020). The concept of open communication among educators can affect their personal development throughout their careers. Principals' role in staff relationships helps explain the effects of teachers' interpersonal relationships among other colleagues. This study helps to clarify how supervisor-subordinate relationships promote attitudes to improve the work environment. In the case of schools, teacher attitudes improve when principal-teacher relationships in schools create positive, intrinsic affective responses among the staff (Nguyen, 2023).

Teachers' emotional involvement with students in the classroom is driven by a basic psychological need for relatedness or communion (Maas et al., 2022). In fact, teachers may be drawn to the classroom in part. Frustration of the positive relationship between the student and teachers might evoke stress, and in the long run causes changes in the wellbeing of teachers. In addition, a study in 2011 asserts that it may be difficult for teachers to provide support to children who require high levels of teacher correction. That is, children who perceive high levels of conflict in their relationships with teachers may also perceive the teacher as emotionally supportive and as liking the student. Because perceptions of the relationship between students and teachers reflect each individual's mental representations of relationships, differences in how perceptions are organized are not unexpected. This agrees with a recent study stressing the importance of a flexible mental representation of teachers to facilitate a positive teacher-student relationship (Bosman et al., 2021).

Moreover, nature and quality of interactions between teachers and children are fundamental to understanding student engagement. It can be assessed through standardized observation methods and can be changed by providing teachers knowledge about developmental processes relevant for classroom interactions that might result in further boost of self-esteem between the educator and mentees (Hofkens et al., 2023). A closer understanding of teachers' relatedness to students in the classroom may not only provide new insights in teachers' wellbeing, ongoing professional development, and retention but also offers indirect yields for students' school success. Consideration of teacher-student relationships as a core aspect of the teaching profession and provision of adequate professional support for teachers to enhance their security of their affiliation in the life of the student and the relational pedagogy will contribute to educational outcomes because good relationships between teachers and students are central to learning and instruction (Allen et al., 2021; Vanner et al., 2022).

The nature of work, salary satisfaction, and quality supervision are significant predictors of organizational commitment and job satisfaction. If a teacher is satisfied with his job, he will be less likely to fail, thus enjoying the benefits and authority that comes with a job. This agrees with a study by Song & Ke (2022) that educational institutions should prioritize human resource construction and incentive methods to improve job satisfaction and enhance employees' organizational commitment. Moreover, a study on the teachers of the Division of Cotabato City in 2013 displays a high level of performance-related skills, abilities, initiatives, and productivity, exceeding requirements in many areas of work performance. This implies that the teachers of Cotabato City are satisfied with their job and that it is a productive one. Furthermore, if the teachers were content with their job, they would develop and maintain a high level of performance. Teaching the learning process makes it more efficient and effective, which could produce highly competitive learners. This notion is supported by the study of Limos-Galay et al. (2023) showing that job satisfaction can improve teacher performance.

The need arises for teachers who demonstrate effective teaching methods and embrace beneficial strategies and practices. Such teachers should possess a genuine love for their profession, wherein 'love' encompasses both a fondness for their work and deriving positive satisfaction from engaging with students and colleagues. Moreover, they should exhibit a sense of competence, feeling capable of surmounting the challenges encountered in the field of teaching (Vanner et al., 2022). Regardless of the level of effort exerted, individuals cannot attain fulfillment unless they possess a genuine passion for their occupation. A research study reveals that teachers' sense of alignment with their values, coupled with supportive supervision and positive relationships with colleagues and parents, proved to be influential factors contributing to their sense of belonging. Conversely, factors such as time pressure and disciplinary issues were linked to emotional exhaustion. Furthermore, consistent with expectations, both a sense of belonging and emotional exhaustion among teachers significantly influenced job satisfaction, while emotional exhaustion and job satisfaction affected their motivation to remain in the teaching profession (Ortan et al., 2021; Schulze-Hagenest et al., 2023).

It is possible that some teachers' "resistance" to technology integration is a function of a negative affective response to technology. Teacher failure in technological innovation is rising only among the senior teachers. Though educational technologies have been considered beneficial in learning, this innovation poses great challenges to teachers who lack the training and resources in accessing such technologies. A study had presented the level of stress and anxiety that educational technology use can affect teachers (Batanero et al., 2021).

There are three propositions anchored in this study. Emotional intelligence, interpersonal support, and self-efficacy are linked to the teacher's model of self-concept.

Emotional intelligence is a talent that can be used in the classroom (Badarun et al., 2020) Four of the key emotional-related talents that make up emotional intelligence include perception or expression of emotion, use of emotion to facilitate thinking, understanding emotion, and self-management of emotion. Emotional intelligence also encompasses the ability to engage information processing from yourself to others and apply it to thought and conduct. These increase learners'

academic status or teachers' work performance, develop healthier relationships, and improve teachers' mental health (Caruso et al., 2019).

Interpersonal relationships in education help improve teaching. According to Vanner et al (2022) and Yu et al. (2023), interpersonal relationships between parents or caregivers, teachers, and peers affect the outcomes of the student's academic performance. It gives them an understanding of the educational phenomena that, if they result in positive attachments between them, may enhance social, emotional, and intellectual function that improves teachers' effectiveness, self-worth, and self-esteem. Principal-teacher interactions affect teachers' effectiveness. Both create the atmosphere or climate for learning and influence not just the students but the school's effectiveness. The leadership of the principal, who has a vision for the school, strongly affects teachers' attitudes as well as the school climate (Echon & Cabal, 2022).

In the Theory of Teacher Attrition in 1993, a shortage of teachers could be solved through compensation policy initiatives that can increase quality and retention of teachers, such as the increase of salaries to be more competitive with other occupations, pay plans for shortage areas, and non-salary initiatives. Many who have graduated from college end up in a different field because the salary of the occupation they were going to apply to is not high. These competitions in the salary of such jobs cause the number of educators to lessen, and thus, government support is essential. It gives a teacher attrition theory that explains what patterns to expect in teacher attrition and turnover, as well as why some teacher attrition is unavoidable (Noel & Finocchio, 2022). A key flaw in human capital theory is the assumption that an individual has perfect knowledge about compensation, benefits, and nonmonetary features of the job. The process of looking for and accepting a job takes place in an uncertain atmosphere. Also, co-teaching helps teachers educate students (Billingsley & Bettini, 2019).

Teachers' self-efficacy is linked to scholastic achievement as educators (Barni et al., 2019). Self-efficacy is also a self-management system that oversees the proper application of professional abilities and knowledge. Self-efficacy is used as a pivot point in teacher development and can provide insight into how and why teachers grow (Daria, 2023). This increases teacher effectiveness and competence while also improving student results. As a result, this theory will aid the study in limiting the scope within certain variables and domains to specify the outcome and data collected.

Four hypothesized models were treated for the best fit in this study that may contribute to the self-concept model of secondary public-school teachers in Region XI. Furthermore, the first conceptual paradigm demonstrates the direct influence of exogenous variables, namely emotional intelligence, interpersonal relationships, and self-efficacy dimensions, towards the endogenous variable, the effectiveness of teachers, supported by the theories and review of related literature.

The first exogenous variable is the interpersonal support measured by four indicators: parent, principal, government, and co-teachers (Keltly & Wakabayashi, 2020). Parent refers to the biological parents, guardian, or anyone who is related and takes care of the student or child (Persson, 2019). Principal refers to the head, school act, associate, vice principal, or assistant principal, and the leader of the school (Sumiran et al., 2022). Government refers to the republic with presidential form, which is divided equally into three branches: executive, which consists of the President and Vice President of the country and carries out and enforces laws; legislative, which also comprises the Congress that is authorized to make the laws; and judicial, which interprets the laws, decides if the law is violated, and applies laws, which is also comprised of the Supreme Court (GovPH, n.d.). Co-teachers refer to the fellow teachers of a learning community (Davis, 2019).

The second exogenous variable is emotional intelligence, measured by five indicators: self-awareness, self-regulation, social skills, empathy, and motivation (Cherry, 2023). Self-awareness refers to the consciousness of oneself (Dhan, 2019). Self-regulation refers to the ability to control emotions that involve four dimensions: a standard of desirable behavior, motivation to meet standards, monitoring of situations and thoughts that forego breaking standards, and willpower, allowing one's internal strength to control urges (Baumesiter, 2019). Social skills refer to the communication within people that has five dimensions: peer relational skills, self-management skills, academic skills, compliance skills, and assertion skills (Salimi et al., 2021). Empathy refers to a person's ability to understand another person and has three categories: cognitive, compassionate, and emotional empathy (Pang et al., 2022). Motivation refers to drives that move people and has eleven types: competence and learning, attitude, achievement, arousal, physiological, incentive, fear, power, affiliation, social, expectancy, and equity motivation (Tarver, 2019).

The third exogenous variable is self-efficacy, measured by four indicators: mastery experiences or personal experiences; observation; persuasion; and emotion (Cherry, 2023b). Personal experiences refer to similar scenarios' experiences encountered (Halverson & Halley, 2023). Observation is defined as monitoring something or someone to gain tactics that could be casual and scientific, subjective and objective, natural, direct or indirect, participant and non-participant, structured and unstructured, and controlled and non-controlled (Jhangiani et al., 2019). Persuasion refers to convincing and is

composed of three modes by Aristotle: ethos, or character; pathos, or emotion; and logos, or discourse (Osman et al., 2021). Emotion refers to one's mood or strong feelings that have two dimensions: valence, or negative and positive, and arousal, or low and high (Adolphs et al. (2019).

The latent endogenous variable is the self-concept model for teachers. This model is one of the most important constructs that could obtain desirable outcomes in the academic performance of the students and the teacher's effectiveness (Maksimovic & Osmanovic, 2019).

A multivariate statistical analysis technique is needed to analyze each variable and their relationships; thus, structural equation modeling (SEM) is used to obtain the relationship between measured variables and latent constructs. In the study, there are two hypotheses formulated showing the causal dependence between the hypothesized models of two latent constructs', namely the exogenous and endogenous variables.

Further, the hypothesized model above shows the following: the oval shapes represent the latent variables to be measured in the study; the rectangular figures connected from the oval are the manifest variables; the circle shows the error variance or disturbance term; the single-headed arrow represents the regression or directional path; and the double-headed arrow signifies covariance.

Hypothesized model 1, represented as Figure 1, indicates the direct causal relation of latent exogenous variables towards endogenous variables. This indicates through a single-headed arrow that interpersonal support, emotional intelligence, and self-efficacy are connected to self-concept. Furthermore, the rectangular shapes represent the eta, or measured variables, of the corresponding exogenous variables, and the lambda, or causal effect, of the indicator.

Figure 1: The Conceptual Framework of the Study

Legend:

par – Parents	mot – Motivation	ips – Instructional Practices and Support
gov – Government	EI – Emotional Intelligence	SE – Self-efficacy
pri – Principal	time –Time	com – Competence
ct – Co-Teachers	fr – Facilities and Resources	ip – Interpersonal Perception
IS – Interpersonal Support	csi – Community Support and Involvement	ari – Acceptance of Risk and Initiatives
sa – Self Awareness	msc – Managing Students' Content	rs – Relationship with Students
sr – Self-Regulation	tl – Teacher's Leadership	sat – Satisfaction
ss –Social Skills	sl – School Leadership	sacc – Self-Acceptance
emp – Empathy	pd – Professional Development	SC –Self-Concept

In consideration of the foregoing assumptions, the researcher has not come across a study that dealt on a structural equation model on school self-concept in public schools in the local setting. It is in this setting that the researcher is interested to determine whether the factors such as interpersonal support, emotional intelligence, and self-efficacy significantly influence self-concept in public school teachers in Region XI, Philippines as this can increase concern to the intended beneficiaries of this study and possibly develop action plans to boost interpersonal support, emotional intelligence, and self-efficacy and consequently enhance self-concept thus, the need to conduct this study.

Accordingly, the main thrust of this study was to determine the best fit structural equation model of self-concept as figured out by interpersonal support, emotional intelligence, and self-efficacy in public teachers in Region XI. Furthermore, this study aimed to describe the first level of interpersonal support of teachers in terms of *parents, government, principal and co-teachers*. Second, this study aimed to ascertain the level of emotional intelligence of teachers in terms of *self-awareness, self-regulation, social skills, empathy and motivation*. Third, it aimed to determine the level of self-efficacy of teachers in terms of *time, facilities and resources, community support and involvement, managing student's content, teachers' leadership, school leadership, professional development, instructional practices and support*. Fourth, it aimed to determine the level of self-concept in terms of *competence, interpersonal perception, acceptance of risks and initiatives, relationship with students, satisfaction, self-acceptance*. Fifth, it aimed to determine the significance of the relationship between the interpersonal support and self-concept, between emotional intelligence and self-concept, and between self-efficacy and self-concept. Lastly, it aimed to determine the structural equation model best fits for the school effectiveness.

This study will benefit people internationally, especially in fields where teachers are involved. The study shall impose support for the self-concept of teachers who are not competent enough and help them instruct students efficiently and effectively. As mentioned, students' intellectual, physical, social, emotional, and behavioral well-being are all influenced by effective instruction. When all education stakeholders, including parents, lawmakers, community members, and educators, share responsibility for continual improvement and student accomplishment, the most effective teaching occurs. Effective teaching is one of the primary engines for school improvement. Teachers are one of the most important factors in any school (Toropova et al., 2019).

The study will inform teachers about models for self-concept in Region XI. It will also help teachers improve their effectiveness. Future researchers will benefit from this study, for it will give them information related to the study that they will conduct in the near future. Additionally, this study will help teachers focus on their cognitive and thinking aspects of themselves, which are the basis for their motivation and create an ideal self that causes drive for behavior. It will help to maximize outcomes by knowing this information, which could lead to more effective academic achievement.

Moreover, this study may improve teachers' knowledge about aspects to be improved in themselves as educators. If workers with emotional intelligence are able to work with groups and adapt or adjust to changes, regardless of their degree, the outcome will be successful. It would also help them to analyze the concept of self-efficacy, which may influence them to identify and know goals to set for themselves that affect their level of persistence and effort in tasks they are given. It would also help them in their productivity (Andreev, 2022).

Additionally, this study might help other people help teachers. Parents would be aware of their responsibility to their students and the need for teacher collaboration to help them achieve academic outcomes. The principal and co-teacher will also be aware of the impact of collaboration between them that could help them pursue their vision and goals as educators and stakeholders. This study might also address the government to reach out for support for the teachers.

2. METHOD

This chapter presents the research respondents, materials/instruments, research design, and procedures as applicable.

Research Respondent

This study was administered in public secondary schools in Region XI. This region consists of 7 division schools, namely, Davao Oriental, Davao City, Davao Occidental, Davao del Norte, Davao del Sur, Davao de Oro, and Island City Garden of Samal. In this study, the respondents were teachers from different public secondary schools in Region XI.

The region is employed with a total of 41,084 active teachers. The number of teachers for each division was determined through stratified random sampling. After stratification, the sample size of 400 secondary teachers was determined from various schools in the Davao Region, who served as respondents for the research. It is in adherence to the important

guideline for determining the appropriate number of participants for Structural Equation Modeling (Savalei, 2021), which is between 200 and 400, at the 0.5 significance level. Stratified random sampling involves the division of a population into smaller sub-groups known as strata. In stratified random sampling or stratification, the strata are formed based on members' shared attributes or characteristics such as income or educational attainment. Stratified random sampling is also called proportional random sampling or quota random sampling. The questionnaire was administered through a Google Form. This approach ensured a diverse representation of secondary teachers in the Davao Region, offering valuable insights into their experiences and perspectives.

Moreover, the researcher considered the inclusion and exclusion criteria in the selection of the respondents of the study. The teacher respondents were the regular teachers among public secondary schools in Region XI whose plantilla numbers were in the Department of Education. These teachers were willing to submit themselves and were permitted by their school heads to undergo the survey to be conducted. Those teachers who voluntarily agreed with the informed consent were included in the survey, hence, teachers who confessed their denial were excluded from the study. This study excluded those teachers coming from private schools. Further, the researcher considered teachers who decided to withdraw or back out during the actual administration of the survey questionnaires.

Materials and Instrument

The adapted survey questionnaires from the studies of Zandyliet et al. (2014), Johnson et al. (2017), Ugoani et al. (2015), and van Dinther et al. (2011) were restructured, modified, and validated with the help of five expert validators to make them more applicable to the current local setting. The first draft of the research instrument was submitted to the research adviser for comments, suggestions, and recommendations on how to improve its presentation, as well as his corrections, which were included and integrated. Final copies were sent to a panel of specialists for review. The final draft incorporated the errors, comments, and suggestions provided by the expert validators before data collection. The combined expert results yielded an average weighted mean of 4.71, with a verbal assessment of *excellent*. Furthermore, before administering the research instrument, pilot testing was conducted with selected teachers who were not study participants. The survey questionnaire for the pilot test was tested for reliability using the Internal Consistency Method. This was the most acceptable strategy to utilize because the test comprises dichotomously scored items that the examinee can pass or fail. Using Cronbach Alpha, the instrument's estimated reliability was 0.970 for the model of self-concept of teachers questionnaire, 0.980 for the emotional intelligence questionnaire, 0.960 for the interpersonal support questionnaire, and 0.985 for the self-efficacy questionnaire.

Design and Procedure

As stated by Bhat (2019), quantitative research is defined as the systematic observable study of an unusual event or a rare and significant event by assembling quantifiable data and performing statistical methods. It accumulates information from existing and potential customers using sampling, online surveys, online polls, etc. After careful analysis of their numbers, they can predict the future of a product or service and make changes accordingly.

Firstly, the study involves the descriptive correlation method Abule and Miralles (2023). Description research demonstrates relationships and describes "what is" or "what was". It is effective for determining variables and hypothetical constructs that can be further studied through other means, and the findings can be used as an indirect test of a theory. Correlation research explores relationships between variables that help determine to what degree a relationship exists between the quantified variables.

Secondly, structural equation modeling, or SEM, is used in the study. Structural equation modeling is described as a group of methodologies that aim to illustrate hypotheses about observed data in terms of a narrow number of structural parameters defined by hypothesized conceptual models (Kaplan, 2000). Factor analysis, regression, and causal analysis are being used to analyze the data. Factor analysis identifies the latent variable or constructs indicated in the structural equation modeling that simplifies the data. Regression analysis involves mathematically sorting variables that show impact to indicate which factors or variables matter most or can be ignored (Altikriti & Anderson, 2021). Moreover, this research uses a causal-comparative design that determines the relationship between the variables, both independent and dependent.

Structural equation modeling (SEM) is used to obtain the relationship between measured variables and latent constructs. In the study, there are two hypotheses formulated showing the casual dependence between the hypothesized models of two latent constructs, namely the exogenous and endogenous variables

To ascertain the best-fit model, the following indices were employed along with their respective criteria.

INDEX	CRITERION
Chi-Square / Degrees of	$0 < \text{value} < 2$
P-value	$> .05$
Normed Fit Index (NFI)	$> .95$
Tucker-Lewis Index (TLI)	$> .95$
Comparative Fit Index (CFI)	$> .95$
Goodness of Fit Index (GFI)	$> .95$
Root Mean Square of Error Approximation (RMSEA)	$< .05$
P of Close Fit (P-close)	$> .05$

Four parts of data are needed for the study: a model of self-concept for teachers, emotional intelligence, interpersonal support, and self-efficacy. Based on our related literature, this study utilized a survey questionnaire to gather the needed data.

The survey of self-concept was adapted from Zandvliet et al. (2014). The said instrument was designed to measure self-concept based on four dimensions: interpersonal relationships, emotional intelligence, and self-efficacy. The survey on interpersonal support was adapted from Johnson et al. (2017). The said instrument was designed to measure interpersonal support based on 4 factors parent, principal, government, and co-teachers.

Moreover, the survey on emotional intelligence was adapted from Ugoani et al. (2015). The said instrument was designed to measure emotional intelligence based on 5 dimensions namely, self-regulation, self-awareness social skills, empathy, and motivation while the survey on self-efficacy was adapted from van Dinther et al. (2010). The said instrument was designed to measure self-efficacy based on 4 dimensions namely; mastery experiences or personal experiences, observation, persuasion, and emotion.

The scale employed for interpreting the means of interpersonal support, emotional intelligence, self-efficacy, and self-concept is in the following ranges: 4.20-5.00 is considered very high/always observed; 3.40-4.19 regarded as high/oftentimes observed; 2.60-3.39 regarded as moderate/sometimes observed; 1.80-2.59 considered to be low/rarely observed and finally, 1.00-1.79 noted as very low/not observed.

The procedures were conducted to gather the data that were essential to this study. Firstly, the researcher asked for permission from the Regional Director down to the Schools Division Superintendents from different divisions of Region XI. Secondly, the formulated survey was produced to be answered by selected public secondary teachers. The link was sent to different school divisions in charge in the Davao region. Thirdly, the venue and time for the survey were set for July 25-29, 2022, at different schools in Region XI. Lastly, the collected data were analyzed, interpreted, and evaluated.

The study used the following statistical tools to interpret the results of the study: Mean, to measure the central tendency calculated by dividing the sum of the scores specifically this will be referring to the quantified level of interpersonal support, emotional intelligence, self-efficacy, and model of self-concept for teachers. Pearson Product Moment Correlation to measure and describe the path or direction of the variables. This was used to identify the interrelationship between quantified level of interpersonal support, emotional intelligence self-efficacy, and model of self-concept for teachers. Structural Equation Modeling or SEM was used in the study to describe the hypothetical relationship between the latent exogenous variables and endogenous variables. This also involves factor analysis, regression, and causal analysis (Gray, 2016).

This study prioritized ethical considerations and received permission from the UM Ethics Review Committee (UMERC) following a thorough review. To preserve respondents' privacy, participation was voluntary and anonymous, and detailed information was supplied to help them make educated selections. The Data Privacy Act of 2012 ensured privacy and secrecy while protecting instructors' personal information. Informed permission was obtained, with an emphasis on voluntariness, to ensure participants' comprehension and rights.

Recruitment required thorough evaluation of parties, risk assessment, and mitigation strategies. Recruiting parties, including school principals and teachers that assisted in responder recruitment, controlled the discomfort. The study had little risks, prioritized participant rights, and provided significant insights for teachers. Respondents enjoyed practical benefits, and safety was secured by pseudonyms, which reinforced confidentiality. The collected data was kept private and utilized to confirm study conclusions.

To avoid plagiarism, the researcher employed turn-it-in software to verify there was no trace or evidence of misrepresenting someone else's work as his own. The researcher ensured that all concepts from other writers and researchers were properly cited. To be able to do so, this document was grammatically checked using Grammarly software. Because this study was based on multiple previous investigations, the researcher made certain that he did not create from his literature. Thus, everything of the information supplied was meticulously recorded and cited. All sources used in this study came from reliable journals and other scholarly works. This research complied with the citation rules set forth of APA 7th edition citation format hence there was

Furthermore, because the researcher is a public-school teacher in the proposed research area, there is a conflict of interest (COI). As a result, the researcher took steps to avoid conflict of interest, such as not surveying his peers and coworkers. Furthermore, there was no set of circumstances under which a professional judgment about a primary interest, such as the respondents' welfare or the validity of the research, would be impacted by a secondary interest, such as financial or academic advantages or recognition. The papers in this paper used no sort of deception to harm the respondents' well-being. The team of specialists reviewed and validated all of the written information. Furthermore, deception was avoided because there was no indication that the advantage

The researcher also ensured that the schools gave their approval. The researcher stated that they obtained written authorization from the organization that conducted the research or the site where the data was collected. When obtaining written permission, the researcher spoke with the School Division Superintendent and the relevant School Heads to grant the permission requested and to demonstrate that the activities were planned well in advance. Also, the survey questionnaires utilized in this study were clear and comprehensible; the researcher made sure that the respondents were fully aware of the benefits the school may get from the study's results through informed consent. Thus, the survey was carried out with the approval of the relevant school officials and the consent of the respondents.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Presented here are the findings on the interpersonal support, emotional intelligence, self-efficacy, and self-concept of secondary public high school teachers in Region XI. The presentations are arranged as follows: the level of interpersonal support given to secondary public high school teachers; the level of emotional intelligence of secondary public high school teachers; the level of self-efficacy of secondary public high school teachers; and the level of self-concept of secondary public high school teachers. Furthermore, the standard deviation of the mean scores on the levels of the identified variables.

The Level of Interpersonal Support Given to Secondary Public High School Teachers

Presented in Table 1 are the data on the level of interpersonal support of secondary public-school teachers in Region XI in terms of the 4 dimensions namely: parents, government, principal, and co-teachers.

As shown in Table 1, the overall mean rating is 4.37, which is described as very high. Describing the results further, an overall standard deviation of 0.479 explains that there is least variability among the means and the ratings of the respondents are homogenous. However, among the indicators of interpersonal support, parents have the highest mean of 4.56 with the smallest standard deviation of 0.506. The government has the lowest mean of 4.25 which is described as very high.

Generally, the level of interpersonal support given by the stakeholders to secondary public-school teachers is always observed. This very high level is contributed from the four (4) indicators namely: parents; government; principal; and co-

Table 1: Level of Interpersonal Support

Indicator	SD	Mean	D.E.
Parents	0.506	4.56	Very High
Government	0.715	4.25	Very High
Principal	0.769	4.32	Very High
Co-Teachers	0.702	4.34	Very High
Overall	0.479	4.37	Very High

teachers. This means that stakeholders are always willing to help teachers reach their full potential. Moreover, majority of parents consistently think highly of the teachers. The government also had a high level of support provided.

Respondents demonstrate in their responses that these indicators are relevant to effective interpersonal support for secondary teachers, particularly in public schools where morale must be boosted on a regular basis. Thus, it is implied that the respondents also show the effectiveness of the interpersonal support given by the indicators as they experienced it. This helps the study prove how crucial interpersonal support is for secondary public-school teachers.

This claim is supported by Meador (2019), who stated that students' learning does not only rely on the teaching of the teachers inside the campus, but that they also learn from the community they are involved with, given that the teachers also needed support not just inside the school but also from the members of the community.

Also, Bongcayat and Guhao (2020) reveal in their study that work engagement and technology leadership is significant to each other. In accordance with these variables mentioned, this also reveals that support to the non-teaching personnel or even teaching personnel shows that their work engagement can be a factor towards their obligation as a teacher for the students. Thus, it also shows that their indicators such as communication skills and vigor are highly relevant to each other, this indicates the support through communication also helps their strength in continuing to teach the students efficiently.

The Level of Emotional Intelligence of Secondary Public High School Teachers

The data on the emotional intelligence of secondary public-school teachers in Region XI in terms of the five dimensions—self-awareness, self-regulation, social skills, empathy, and motivation—is presented in Table 2.

The entire mean rating is 4.27, which is very high, as seen in Table 2. The results are further explained by an aggregate standard deviation of 0.483, which shows that there is little variation in the means and that the respondents' ratings are homogeneous. However, self-awareness has the greatest mean of 4.51 (very high) and the lowest standard deviation of 0.482 among all the emotional intelligence measures. The lowest mean, 4.11, is considered high for empathy.

The overall mean of emotional intelligence among secondary public-school teachers in Region XI is rated as very high. This means that teachers always have the capacity to identify, control, and understand their own emotions as well as those of others. Among the indicators of emotional intelligence, self-awareness has a very high level and is ranked as the highest. This means that teachers consistently believed that education should be anchored to students' needs, sought ways to improve their performance, worked to become effective teachers, took personal responsibility for meeting the students' learning needs, and publicly admitted their mistakes. Empathy, on the other hand, has both the lowest ranking and the highest level. This indicates

Table 2: Level of Emotional Intelligence

Indicators	SD	Mean	D.E.
Self-Awareness	0.482	4.51	Very High
Self-Regulation	0.521	4.38	Very High
Social Skills	0.550	4.23	Very High
Empathy	0.573	4.11	High
Motivation	0.617	4.13	High
Overall	0.483	4.27	Very High

that teachers believe they have less ability to see problems from someone else's perspective. They can, less generally, strategize projects to fit the situation when necessary. They thought that it was not difficult to understand the non-verbal messages of co-teachers and students. They have less comprehension of informal groups and less comprehension of historical reasons for workplace issues.

This is supported by Ezzi's (2019) assertion that, as emotions are usually involved in every person's action, they also influence human intelligence, which handles our capacity to think and understand. This demonstrates the significance of emotional intelligence for teachers, as it enables them to deal with situations that require their guidance and attention. Also, Schunk et al. (2022) stated that interacting with and controlling what you feel explains how emotions and intelligence are correlated with each other.

Based on a study, there is a strong correlation between psychological empowerment and job satisfaction among non-teaching staff members at private higher education institutions in Region XII. This demonstrates the high degree of empowerment and work satisfaction among non-teaching staff at private higher education institutions in Region XII. The manner they go about their work shows how content they are with the work they do for their organization (Songcog and Guhao, 2020). This shows that the teachers with psychological empowerment in relevant to their emotional quotient, they are satisfied with their job.

The Level of Self-efficacy of Secondary Public High School Teachers

As shown in Table 3, the level of self-efficacy of secondary public-school teachers was assessed using the following indicators: time, facilities, and resources; community support and involvement; managing students' content; teachers' leadership; school leadership; professional development; and instructional practices and support.

Results revealed that the overall mean of self-efficacy is 4.35, which is described as very high with a standard deviation of 0.518. resulted in an overall mean of 4.35, described as very high, with a standard deviation of 0.518. This shows that there is little variation in the means and that the respondents' ratings are homogeneous. Among the indicators of self-efficacy, teacher leadership has the highest mean of 4.51 (Very high level) and the smallest standard deviation of 0.590. Facilities and resources have the lowest mean of 4.02 (High level) with a standard deviation of 0.721.

The overall level of self-efficacy of secondary public-school teachers in Region XI is rated very high, meaning that this is always observed. This implies that teachers' confidence to carry out the required behaviors in order to achieve the standard teaching performance is apparent. Teacher leadership has a very high level of self-efficacy indicators. This implies that they firmly believed that they were effective

Table 3: Level of Self-Efficacy

Indicators	SD	Mean	D.E.
Time	0.577	4.24	Very High
Facilities and Resources	0.721	4.02	High
Community Support and Involvement	0.649	4.43	Very High
Managing Student's Content	0.591	4.43	Very High
Teachers' Leadership	0.590	4.51	Very High
School Leadership	0.681	4.45	Very High
Professional Development	0.596	4.43	Very High
Instructional Practices and Support	0.600	4.32	Very High
Overall	0.518	4.35	Very High

leaders at school. They are being trusted to make professional, sound decisions about instruction. They are being recognized as educational experts. They are also encouraged to participate in school leadership roles. Conversely, facilities and resources obtained the lowest ranking. This means teachers believe there is insufficient availability of internet connections and instructional technology resources such as computers, printers, phones, fax machines, email, paper, pens, software, and internet access at school. They also affirmed that there is no adequate space for them to work productively.

In support to the top indicator of self-efficacy, Rahmawati (2021) observed a significant relationship between self-efficacy and teacher leadership of secondary school teachers in West Jakarta. However, highlighted that the surrounding environment and collaborators maintain support to the teachers to pave the way for the development of their leadership skills.

A conducive teaching environment is paramount for the satisfaction and effectiveness of public-school teachers (Masoom, 2021b). When considering the school environment, it becomes evident that a positive setting equipped with ample learning materials and resources, such as internet access, printers, and computers, plays a pivotal role in increasing teacher efficacy.

Guhao (2016) shows in the study that there is a high level of self-efficacy among the public teachers in Region XI as well as the correlation of conversational leadership of the school heads and the self-efficacy of the teachers. This suggests that if teachers are given the opportunity to grow their self-efficacy, they will be more motivated, fulfilled, effective in the classroom, and efficient in their school performances. Also, this support that in order for the teachers to have motivation in their job, self-efficacy can help by improving and developing it.

The Level of Self-concept of Secondary Public High School Teachers

As depicted in Table 4, the level of self-concept of secondary public-school teachers in Region XI is low. This self-concept is measured through competence, interpersonal perception, acceptance of risks and initiatives, relationships with students, satisfaction, and self-acceptance.

Generally, the level of self-concept of secondary public-school teachers is high (Mean = 3.95). The standard deviation of self-concept is 0.478, which explains a little variation in the means and indicates that the respondents' ratings are homogeneous. Among the indicators of self-concept, relationships with students have the highest mean of 4.45 (Very high) with a standard deviation of 0.598, while satisfaction has the lowest mean of 2.87 (Moderate) with a standard deviation of 1.057.

The overall level of the self-concept of secondary public-school teachers in Region XI is high, indicating that this is oftentimes observed. This implies that teachers

Table 4: Level of Self-Concept

Indicators	SD	Mean	D.E.
Competence	0.542	4.24	Very High
Interpersonal Perception	0.585	4.34	Very High
Acceptance of Risks and Initiatives	0.643	4.04	High
Relationship with Students	0.598	4.45	Very High
Satisfaction	1.057	2.87	Moderate
Self-Acceptance	0.741	3.76	High
Overall	0.478	3.95	High

were confident in their perception of their actions, skills, and distinguishing characteristics in relation to the situation. Specifically, among the indicators of self-concept, relationships with students have a very high level. With this, teachers believed

that student-teacher relationships were always secure. They always believed in the full confidence of their students. They always enjoy their class and hold it in high regard. Nonetheless, satisfaction is moderate. This denotes that teacher sometimes have difficulty being successful because of their current situations. They sometimes think that their teaching performance is not satisfactory. They also sometimes believed they would change their profession if given a chance because they could not stand by themselves.

Research demonstrates the intricate relationship between teachers' self-concept and their interactions with students. As teachers encourage students and help them develop confidence, they concurrently enhance their own self-concept. This mutual reinforcement leads to a symbiotic relationship where teachers, in guiding students to become effective learners, also refine their teaching methods and overall competence (Yeung, Craven, and Kaur, 2014). Building upon this understanding, a recent study conducted by Low et al. (2019) highlights that teacher with positive self-concepts, fueled by their passion, interest, and enjoyment in teaching, exhibit a continuous willingness to engage with even the most behaviorally and academically challenging students. Bayawa and Guhao (2022) stated in their study that it generally suggests a substantial association between principal instructional management, school atmosphere, teachers' personalities, and instructors' self-efficacy. This demonstrates how the management of the school head is related to the personality or self-concept of the teacher. As a result, it demonstrates how the school head assists the teachers in boosting their self-concept. This will have an impact on the relationship between the teachers and students because they can adapt the governance of the school inside their classroom.

Significance on the Relationship between Levels of Interpersonal Support and Self-Concept

Reflected in Table 5 is the significant relationship between levels of interpersonal support and self-concept of public-school teachers in Region XI. The result exhibits that relationship between interpersonal support and self-concept of teachers exists. With an overall p-value of 0.000 which is less than 0.05, the relationship is significant at α 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis is hereby rejected. Also, as evident in the p-value of 0.000, the relationship between the indicators of interpersonal support and the indicators of self-concept are significant at α 0.05 level of significance except for

satisfaction indicator. The overall correlation coefficient value between interpersonal support and self-concept is 47.9% which denotes moderately positive correlation. When the individual indicators of interpersonal support was correlated with the overall means of self-concept, the r values ranged from 0.280 to 0.465 with all p-values= 0.000 which were less than 0.05, therefore, all exhibited significant correlations. Among the indicators of interpersonal support and self-concept, "parents and relationship with students" have the highest correlation coefficient of 63.5% which signifies positively high correlation.

Table 5: Significance on the Relationship between Levels of Interpersonal Support and Self-Concept

Interpersonal Support	Self-Concept						Overall
	Competence	Interpersonal Perception	Acceptance of Risks and Initiatives	Relationship with Students	Satisfaction	Self-Acceptance	
Parents	.535* (0.000)	.559* (0.000)	.442* (0.000)	.635* (0.000)	-.064 (0.204)	.164* (0.001)	.465* (0.000)
Government	.226* (0.000)	.182* (0.000)	.173* (0.001)	.161* (0.001)	.199* (0.000)	.211* (0.000)	.280* (0.000)
Principal	.312* (0.000)	.377* (0.000)	.317* (0.000)	.433* (0.000)	-.052 (0.296)	.121* (0.015)	.309* (0.000)
Co-Teachers	.325* (0.000)	.469* (0.000)	.350* (0.000)	.432* (0.000)	-.003 (0.955)	.093 (0.063)	.348* (0.000)
Overall	.470* (0.000)	.539* (0.000)	.437* (0.000)	.560* (0.000)	.036 (0.478)	.205* (0.000)	.479* (0.000)

*Significant at 0.05 significance level.

Based on the data gathered, the overall result of interpersonal support significantly influences the self-concept of secondary public-school teachers. This means that interpersonal support has a moderately positive relationship with self-concept. This explains why, for every increase in interpersonal support provided by stakeholders to teachers, their level of self-concept rises. Thus, the interpersonal support teachers receive from others influences how much they value their role as teachers to their students. This also implies how critical it is to fulfill and effectively encourage teachers that they are not alone in their efforts to educate students. However, indicators of interpersonal support such as parents, the government, the principal, and co-teachers do not significantly relate to satisfaction as an indicator of the self-concept of teachers. This means that, regardless of the interpersonal support provided to teachers by stakeholders, their level of satisfaction with their profession will never change. Most teachers consider their profession not a vocation but an occupation. They serve not out of passion but out of compliance.

To preserve the quality, capability, and existence in a good social life value order, it begins with the renewal of everyone's personal value order, which is becoming more positive, according to the study done by Ulfa, Zainal, Mayasari, Karim, and Rezki (2022). Positive experiences had by research subjects can be used to understand the dynamics of this study of self-concept, and psychological conditions that occur during communication can be used to understand the dynamics of interpersonal communication. As a result, it illustrates how interpersonal communication influences one's self-concept to help one succeed as a teacher. Additionally, the teachers' interpersonal support is crucial for evaluating their self-concept as per the study.

A person's internalized sense of who they are, what they are capable of, and how other people see them is referred to as their "self-concept." The way people see themselves and others, how they interpret social standards, and even the language they use when communicating to others are all ways that self-concept affects communication (Kelly, 2021). According to this assertion, the instructors' interpersonal support will provide them the freedom to decide how to express their self-concept. Additionally, individuals can improve their interpersonal interactions and sense of self by chatting.

Guhao and Quines (2021) shows in their study that there is significant relationship between teamwork attitude and authentic leadership. This shows how effective leadership would anticipate a specific reflexivity regulatory team phase, which in turn will be connected to two outcomes of team success, namely effectiveness and productivity. Additionally, genuine leadership influenced the collective team actions, resulting in reflexivity in the team process, which in turn helped anticipate the

performance of the team. Thus, this can support the significant relationship of interpersonal support and self-concept of teachers as the authentic leadership can be used as a support to boost the confidence of teachers and their attitude towards their work and students. Further, with the help of leadership support towards the teachers, they can also feel satisfied with their job as well as feel motivated.

Significance on the Relationship between Levels of Emotional Intelligence and Self-Concept

Presented in Table 6, there is a significant relationship between the emotional intelligence and self-concept of the secondary public-school teachers in Region XI. The findings indicate a significant relationship between teachers' emotional intelligence and self-concept (p-value 0.05). The overall correlation coefficient is 74.8%. When the individual indicators of emotional intelligence were correlated with the overall means of self-concept, the r values ranged from 0.641 to 0.690 with all p-values= 0.000 which were less than 0.05, therefore, all exhibited significant correlations. However, among the indicators of emotional intelligence and self-concept, only self-awareness versus satisfaction has a significant relationship.

Table 6: Significance on the Relationship between Levels of Emotional Intelligence and Self-Concept

Emotional Intelligence	Self-Concept						
	Competence	Interpersonal Perception	Acceptance of Risks and Initiatives	Relationship with Students	Satisfaction	Self-Acceptance	Overall
Self-Awareness	.658* (0.000)	.695* (0.000)	.617* (0.000)	.689* (0.000)	.045 (0.370)	.298* (0.000)	.641* (0.000)
Self-Regulation	.685* (0.000)	.708* (0.000)	.649* (0.000)	.663* (0.000)	.115* (0.022)	.352* (0.000)	.690* (0.000)
Social Skills	.599* (0.000)	.645* (0.000)	.610* (0.000)	.587* (0.000)	.204* (0.000)	.339* (0.000)	.666* (0.000)
Empathy	.569* (0.000)	.600* (0.000)	.575* (0.000)	.509* (0.000)	.223* (0.000)	.386* (0.000)	.647* (0.000)
Motivation	.594* (0.000)	.574* (0.000)	.638* (0.000)	.530* (0.000)	.217* (0.000)	.327* (0.000)	.648* (0.000)
Overall	.703* (0.000)	.728* (0.000)	.702* (0.000)	.671* (0.000)	.189* (0.000)	.388* (0.000)	.748* (0.000)

*Significant at 0.05 significance level.

Generally speaking, emotional intelligence was significantly correlated with the self-concept of secondary public-school teachers. This means that emotional intelligence has a highly positive relationship with the self-concepts of teachers. This explains further that for every increase in the level of emotional intelligence of teachers, there is also an increase in their level of self-concept. However, self-awareness as an indicator of emotional intelligence is not significantly related to satisfaction as an indicator of teacher self-concept. This means that, regardless of the strategies used for self-awareness, teachers' satisfaction with their work as teachers will never change. In spite of the orientation of the teachers to encourage the students about the importance of education through making instructional materials that are based on the students' needs, teachers still hold on to their principle that they have unsatisfactory performance at the end of the school year.

A teacher's high emotional intelligence (EQ) fosters an empathetic environment and enables them to effectively motivate and encourage students, ultimately leading to a positive atmosphere conducive to enjoyable learning experiences. This ability not only facilitates effective guidance and interaction with students but also cultivates productive learning outcomes (Cherry, 2019). The recent findings of no significant correlation between self-awareness and self-concept among teachers could be attributed to the prevalence of negative emotions experienced by teachers, such as feelings of helplessness, awareness of their shortcomings, anger, or insecurity. To manage these emotions, teachers often prefer problem-focused coping strategies over emotion-focused ones (Rajesh et al., 2022).

A result of a study shows a significant correlation between principal leadership and work well-being, principal leadership and organizational commitment, principal leadership and organizational climate, organizational commitment and work well-being, and organizational climate and work well-being (Ponsades and Guhao, 2021). This finding supported that there is a significant relationship between the emotional intelligence and self-concept of the teachers. As leadership will be able to help the well-being of the teachers in their school and same goes for their emotional intelligence as it affects their mind

in conducting lectures in their classroom. Also, the study revealed that the well-being of the teachers is always evident, especially in having a good relationship with their administrators and with their students. With this, it shows a significant impact towards the emotional intelligence of the teachers.

Significance on the Relationship between Levels of Self-Efficacy and Self-Concept

As presented in Table 7, there is a significant relationship between the self-efficacy and self-concept of the secondary public-school teachers in Region XI. The findings show a significant relationship (p-value 0.05) between teachers' self-efficacy and self-concept. The overall correlation coefficient is 64.3%. This explains why the overall degree of relationship between self-efficacy and the self-concept of teachers has a moderately positive correlation. When the individual indicators of self-efficacy were correlated with the overall means of self-concept, the r values ranged from 0.451 to 0.591 with all p-values= 0.000 which were less than 0.05, therefore, all exhibited significant correlations. However, among the indicators of self-efficacy and self-concept, professional development versus relationship with students; community support and involvement versus satisfaction; managing students' content versus satisfaction; teachers' leadership versus satisfaction; school leadership versus satisfaction; and professional development versus satisfaction do not have a significant relationship (p-value > 0.05).

Results revealed that self-efficacy is significantly correlated with the self-concept of secondary public-school teachers. This implies that teacher self-efficacy has a moderately positive relationship to teacher self-concept. The enjoyment experienced by teachers in their classes depends on their belief that they are effective leaders at school. Nevertheless, professional development as an indicator of self-efficacy does not significantly relate to relationships with students as an indicator of self-concept. This means that, regardless of the various training and seminars attended by teachers, the relationship of teachers to their students is unaffected. Moreover, indicators of self-efficacy such as community support and involvement, managing students' content, teachers' leadership, school leadership, and professional development do not have a significant connection to satisfaction as an indicator of self-concept. This further explains that even if the teacher provides useful information to parents about student learning, works in a safe school environment, works as an effective leader at school, holds high professional standards for delivering instruction, implements instructional strategies, and meets diverse learning needs, the teacher's perception towards their satisfaction with their performance will never change.

Table 7: Significance on the Relationship between Levels of Self-Efficacy and Self-Concept

Self-Efficacy	Self-Concept						
	Competence	Interpersonal Perception	Acceptance of Risks and Initiatives	Relationship with Students	Satisfaction	Self-Acceptance	Overall
Time	.563* (0.000)	.568* (0.000)	.517* (0.000)	.509* (0.000)	.143* (0.004)	.354* (0.000)	.591* (0.000)
Facilities and Resources	.410* (0.000)	.498* (0.000)	.436* (0.000)	.460* (0.000)	.129* (0.010)	.260* (0.000)	.487* (0.000)
Community Support and Involvement	.478* (0.000)	.533* (0.000)	.437* (0.000)	.587* (0.000)	-.045 (0.374)	.187* (0.000)	.451* (0.000)
Managing Student's Content	.510* (0.000)	.559* (0.000)	.479* (0.000)	.647* (0.000)	-.013 (0.797)	.246* (0.000)	.511* (0.000)
Teachers' Leadership	.570* (0.000)	.577* (0.000)	.495* (0.000)	.627* (0.000)	-.001 (0.986)	.247* (0.000)	.530* (0.000)
School Leadership	.522* (0.000)	.631* (0.000)	.479* (0.000)	.633* (0.000)	-.011 (0.829)	.278* (0.000)	.534* (0.000)
Professional Development	.597* (0.000)	.611* (0.000)	.525* (0.000)	.642* (0.000)	.042 (0.402)	.283* (0.000)	.587* (0.000)
Instructional Practices and Support	.539* (0.000)	.595* (0.000)	.545* (0.000)	.591* (0.000)	.103* (0.039)	.288* (0.000)	.581* (0.000)
Overall	.629* (0.000)	.698* (0.000)	.588* (0.000)	.706* (0.000)	.053 (0.289)	.322* (0.000)	.643* (0.000)

*Significant at 0.05 significance level.

In the educational context, self-efficacy is associated with confidence, as teachers assess their ability to solve problems, while self-concept relates to perceived personal competence in task execution (Bergqvist, 2024). According to Dual et al. (2022) and Pozas et al. (2022), self-concept and self-efficacy positively correlate with subjective well-being in education, highlighting the importance of teachers' roles and their self-efficacy in influencing students' efficiency. Pozas et al. (2022) further emphasize that positive self-concept and self-efficacy are crucial components of teachers' abilities. Although the current study shows a weak relationship between the two variables, it underscores the need for appropriate capacity-building measures, such as training programs, to develop teachers' innate self-concept and self-efficacy.

Best Fit Model on Self-Concept

The original proposed model outlined in Figure 1 requires some modification to fit the data. There were three generated models presented in the study. In identifying the best fit model, all indices included must consistently fall within the acceptable ranges. Chi-square/ degrees of freedom value should be less than 2 but greater than 0 with its corresponding p-value greater than 0.05. Root mean square error approximation value must be less than 0.05 and its corresponding P-close value must be greater than 0.05. The other indices such as the normed fit index, Tucker-Lewis index, comparative fit index and the goodness of fit index must all be greater than 0.95.

Generated Model 1. Figure 2 showed the generated structural model 1. It displays the interrelationships of the exogenous variables: interpersonal support with its four indicators namely: parents, government, principal and co-teachers; emotional intelligence with its five domains specifically: self-awareness, self-regulation, social skills, empathy and motivation; and self-efficacy with time, facilities and resources, community support and involvement, managing students' content, teacher's leadership, school leadership, professional development and instructional practices and support as its indicators; and their causal relationship on the endogenous variable self-concept having six indicators namely: competence, interpersonal perception, acceptance of risk and initiatives, relationship with students, satisfaction and self-acceptance. All indices did not reach the acceptable ranges as shown in table 8. Hence, a poor fit.

Figure 2: Structural Model 1 in Standardized Solution

Legend:

par – Parents	time –Time	com – Competence
gov – Government	fr – Facilities and Resources	ip – Interpersonal Perception
pri – Principal	csi – Community Support and Involvement	ari – Acceptance of Risk and Initiatives
ct – Co-Teachers	msc – Managing Students' Content	rs – Relationship with Students
IS – Interpersonal Support	tl – Teacher's Leadership	sat – Satisfaction
sa – Self Awareness	sl – School Leadership	sacc – Self-Acceptance
sr – Self-Regulation	pd – Professional Development	SC –Self-Concept
ss –Social Skills	ips – Instructional Practices and Support	
emp – Empathy	SE – Self-Efficacy	
mot – Motivation		
EI – Emotional Intelligence		

Table 8: Goodness of Fit Measures of Structural Equation Model 1

INDEX	CRITERION	MODEL FIT VALUE
P-Close	> 0.05	.000
CMIN/DF	0 < value < 2	3.834
P-value	> 0.05	.000
GFI	> 0.95	.814
CFI	> 0.95	.908
NFI	> 0.95	.880
TLI	> 0.95	.896
RMSEA	< 0.05	.084

Legend:

CMIN/DF	-	Chi-Square/Degrees of Freedom
NFI	-	Normed Fit Index
TLI	-	Tucker-Lewis Index
CFI	-	Comparative Fit Index
GFI	-	Goodness of Fit Index
RMSEA	-	Root Means Square of Error Approximation
P-close	-	P of Close Fit
P-value	-	Probability Level

Generated Model 2. The generated model 2 is shown in figure 3. It exhibits the interrelationships of the exogenous variables where some indicators with low values were removed.

The interpersonal support got two remaining indicators namely: principal and co-teachers. The eight indicators of emotional intelligence were slashed into three specifically: *self-regulation, empathy and social skills*. While self-efficacy got four remaining domains explicitly: *managing students' content, school leadership, professional development and instructional practices and support* to manifest their causal relationship on the endogenous variable which was the self-concept.

Further, the significant improvement among indices were manifested in model 2 when compared to Model 1, such as: CFI from .908 to .968 which is acceptable; CMIN/DF, from 3.834 to 2.910; GFI, from .814 to .935; NFI, from .880 to .958; TLI, from .896 to .957; RSMEA, from .084 to .069 and P-Close from .000 to .005. While P-value shows the same value of .000 in two models. The model was still found not fit even if CFI, NFI and TLI passed the set criterion, because the other five criteria failed to reach the desired value as exhibited in table 9. Hence, model 2 was a poor fit. For the model to be declared as best fit, it has to pass all the other criteria.

Figure 3. Structural Model 2 in Standardized Solution

Legend

- par – Parents
- gov – Government
- pri – Principal
- ct – Co-Teachers
- IS – Interpersonal Support
- sa – Self Awareness
- sr – Self-Regulation
- ss –Social Skills
- emp – Empathy
- mot – Motivation
- EI – Emotional Intelligence
- time –Time
- fr – Facilities and Resources
- csi – Community Support and Involvement
- msc – Managing Students’ Content
- tl – Teacher’s Leadership
- sl – School Leadership
- pd – Professional Development
- ips – Instructional Practices and Support
- SE – Self-Efficacy
- com – Competence
- ip – Interpersonal Perception
- ari – Acceptance of Risk and Initiatives
- rs – Relationship with Students
- sat – Satisfaction
- sacc – Self-Acceptance
- SC –Self-Concept

Table 9: Goodness of Fit Measures of Structural Equation Model 2

INDEX	CRITERION	MODEL FIT VALUE
P-Close	> 0.05	.005
CMIN/DF	0 < value < 2	2.910
P-value	> 0.05	.000
GFI	> 0.95	.935
CFI	> 0.95	.968
NFI	> 0.95	.958
TLI	> 0.95	.957
RMSEA	< 0.05	.069

Legend:

- CMIN/DF** - Chi-Square/Degrees of Freedom
- NFI** - Normed Fit Index
- TLI** - Tucker-Lewis Index
- CFI** - Comparative Fit Index
- GFI** - Goodness of Fit Index
- RMSEA** - Root Means Square of Error Approximation
- Pclose** - P of Close Fit
- P-value** - Probability Level

Generated Model 3. Lastly, the generated Model 3 exhibited in figure 4 showed the interrelationships of the exogenous variables: *interpersonal support, emotional intelligence and self-efficacy* and their causal relationships on the endogenous variable *self-concept*. This model was a modified version of Models 1 and 2, wherein some indicators with low values were removed.

Figure 4. Structural Model 3 in Standardized Solution.

Legend:

par – Parents	com – Competence	time –Time
gov – Government	ip – Interpersonal Perception	fr – Facilities and Resources
pri – Principal	ari – Acceptance of Risk and Initiatives	csi – Community Support and Involvement
ct – Co-Teachers	rs – Relationship with Students	msc – Managing Students’ Content
IS – Interpersonal Support	sat – Satisfaction	tl – Teacher’s Leadership
sa – Self Awareness	sacc – Self-Acceptance	sl – School Leadership
sr – Self-Regulation	SC –Self-Concept	pd – Professional Development
ss –Social Skills		ips – Instructional Practices and Support
emp – Empathy		SE – Self-Efficacy
mot – Motivation		
EI – Emotional Intelligence		

Table 10: Goodness of Fit Measures of Structural Equation Model 3

INDEX	CRITERION	MODEL FIT VALUE
P-Close	> 0.05	.844
CMIN/DF	0 < value < 2	1.463
P-value	> 0.05	.078
GFI	> 0.95	.983
CFI	> 0.95	.995
NFI	> 0.95	.984
TLI	> 0.95	.991
RMSEA	< 0.05	.034

Legend:

CMIN/DF	-	Chi-Square/Degrees of Freedom
NFI	-	Normed Fit Index
TLI	-	Tucker-Lewis Index
CFI	-	Comparative Fit Index
GFI	-	Goodness of Fit Index
RMSEA	-	Root Means Square of Error Approximation
P-close	-	P of Close Fit
P-value	-	Probability Level

Furthermore, the substantial improvement among indices were manifested in model 3 when compared to Model 2, such as: P-Close, from .005 to .844; CMIN/DF, from 2.910 to 1.463; P-value, .000 to .078; GFI, from .935 to .983; CFI form .968 to .995; NFI, from .958 to .984; TLI, from .957 to .991 and RMSEA .069 to .034. Which all fall within the acceptable ranges.

The self-concept of secondary public high school teachers is significantly affected by interpersonal support, self-efficacy, and emotional intelligence. This means that teachers’ perceptions towards their behavior, abilities, and characteristics can be determined through strategies or activities that are provided by school stakeholders; their own motivation, behavior, and social environment; and their ability to recognize emotions in people around them.

On the other hand, self-concept is dependent on acceptance of risk and initiatives as well as competence. Interpersonal support depends on the principal while emotional intelligence is influenced by self-regulation. Managing student’s content is the result of the teacher's self-efficacy. Thus, this implies how the self-concept is affected by the variables mentioned to determine the teacher’s perception in their ways of teaching or teaching itself. Also, this profession does not only stand as teaching the young ones, but also dealing with the circumstances they are experiencing with relevance with their profession, there is more about teaching.

It supports the idea that teachers' self-perceptions of their own teaching efficiency might be generically referred to as their "teacher self-concept." Researchers have emphasized the significance of teachers' competency beliefs, which are sometimes referred to as self-efficacy or self-concept and may affect psychological factors associated with instructors (Miller, 2020; Lumbantobing, 2020; Gilar-Corbi et al., 2019). Clearly, it is crucial for teacher education programs to make sure preservice teachers have positive views of themselves as instructors. This is significant both as a primary aim in and of itself and as a key mediating factor that can positively influence other desirable outcomes in teaching contexts (Pozas et al., 2022).

As the self-concept is dependent on acceptance and risk initiatives, it is supported that teachers can take the risk especially if they are not doubting their safety in their workplace. Teachers are better to know they are likely to change their pacing in relevance to teaching because of their students, they know that as they change, the better help they can offer to the students in order for them to work hard. Taking the risks and acceptance also involve their creativeness (Henriksen et al. 2021). As well as the competence if the teachers in teaching. Thus, in order for the teachers to fully manifest their skills in teaching in different area, they also need training program to build their competence and be able to help the students who struggle in various of area in their lectures (Pozas et al., 2022).

Moreover, as the interpersonal support depends on the principal, Meador (2019) states that the effectiveness of the teacher can be improved with the help of a supportive principal, as their main role is to provide a collaborative environment for the teachers to fully express their skills. With the help of the principal, who regularly monitors the teacher's performance, trust can be built between them, which is also important for the teachers. Also, as the emotional intelligence of the teachers is dependent on self-regulation, it is indicated by Mamat and Ismail (2021) that through this skill, the students can apply this learning when they also know that the teachers are using it as a tool for planning and reflection.

Furthermore, as managing the students' content results in the teachers' self-efficacy, it is essential to determine in this portion how the teachers effectively maintain harmony in classes. As per Amstad and Muller (2020) and Kollerova et al. (2023) the cause of the lack of collaborative and effective classrooms is the disruptive behaviors of students that result in less academic involvement. With this, it shows that without the self-efficacy of the teachers, the classroom will not be a friendly learning environment for the other students.

A study revealed that teachers have high levels of self-efficacy, which is a sign that they are doing a good job of fostering a positive learning environment for their students. This demonstrates that teachers' self-efficacy is always apparent (Bayawa and Guhao, 2022). This finding also demonstrates how proficient teachers who have strong self-efficacy views are at using classroom management techniques. These teachers tend to use more organized, well-managed, student-centered, and sympathetic classroom management techniques, as well as be more receptive to student suggestions. Teachers who felt more in charge of their classrooms showed higher levels of self-efficacy than those who felt less in control. Positive classroom management techniques are used by teachers who are more effective (Bay, 2020).

4. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the foregoing findings, the researchers had drawn the following conclusions:

There is a very high level of interpersonal support among secondary public-school teachers in Region XI in terms of parents, government, the principal, and co-teachers. Quantitatively, parental support has obtained the highest mean value, while government support obtains the lowest mean value.

Also, there is a very high level of emotional intelligence of the secondary public-school teachers in Region XI with their domains self-awareness, self-regulation, social skills, empathy, and motivation. Based on the findings, self-awareness has gained the highest mean rating and meanwhile empathy has gained the lowest mean rating.

Furthermore, there is a very high level of self-efficacy with its indicators of time, facilities and resources, community support and involvement, managing student's content, teacher's leadership, school leadership, professional development, and instructional practices and support. As per the result, teacher's leadership has the highest mean value and on the other hand, facilities and resources has the lowest mean value. This indicates that teacher's leadership is apparent in terms of the self-efficacy of the teachers rather than the facilities and resources factor.

The researcher also concludes that the interpersonal support, emotional intelligence, and self-efficacy indicators are significantly related with the self-concept indicators of the secondary public-school teachers in Region XI. Thus, the hypotheses of this study are rejected.

The self-concept of secondary public high school teachers is significantly affected by interpersonal support, self-efficacy, and emotional intelligence, confirming the self-concept theory. On the other hand, self-concept is dependent on acceptance of risk and initiatives as well as competence. Interpersonal support depends on the principal, while emotional intelligence is influenced by self-regulation. Managing students' content is the result of the self-efficacy of the teacher.

Based on the conclusions mentioned above, the following are highly recommended:

From the findings of the study, **policy makers** may apply the findings to the relationship between interpersonal support, emotional intelligence, and self-efficacy in relation to teachers' self-concept in terms of improving educational quality and providing full-time support as teachers decide to use various approaches in the educational background. Thus, it is also recommended for them to help the teachers implement programs that will not just improve the environment for the learners but also the organized working environment for the teachers to teach in.

On the other hand, in response to the low level of satisfaction of teachers towards their job, **policy makers** should pass a bill that will compensate the teachers in terms of financial aspects. The teachers' salary should be almost the same with the salary of teachers abroad

The **Department of Education officials** may utilize the results to strengthen the teacher formation program by focusing on the areas of interpersonal skills, emotional intelligence, self-efficacy, and self-concept. In the light of improving principals' instructional management, which has a high degree of influence on the development and establishment of a better organizational culture among teachers, they also strengthen their training on instructional management, particularly on framing and communicating the school goals to stakeholders, coordinating the curriculum for better academic outcomes, protecting instructional time for students' practice of new skills and concepts, maintaining high visibility for fostering immediate feedback and support, promoting professional development for better delivery and facilitation of learning, and finally providing incentives for learning to arouse students' interest and motivate teachers.

It is suggested that **secondary public-school teachers** assess themselves in terms of the interpersonal support they received, their emotional intelligence and self-efficacy, as well as their self-concept, in order to improve their profession and the students' learning progress. Because the results show a significant relationship between the variables involved, it may assist teachers in determining the issues they need to deal with when teaching. This can also be a chance to bring up the feedback of the students on the method of their teaching and what aspect or area needs to be resolved.

It is recommended for the **secondary education students** to take the result of this study, which indicates a significant relationship among the variables involved, as a chance to see teaching in a different light and realize that they also need support and self-assessment to be efficient teachers. Thus, this study will also help them to develop skills and coping mechanisms in regard to their future professions for dealing with the issues in relevance to the following indicators. Furthermore, this will enlighten them not only on how to become a good teacher, but also on how to improve their efficiency and personality in the classroom.

This study may be used by the **students** to utilize new things inside their classroom that will not only help them but also the teachers, with whom they are interacting almost every day. It is highly recommended for them to take the chance to build good relationships with their teachers and, at the same time, pay attention to how the teachers deal with stress in the educational setting.

The results of this study may be used as a reference for **future research** in relation to the variables involved, which are interpersonal support, emotional intelligence, self-efficacy, and self-concept. Moreover, this study can also give them ideas in different areas in regard to the secondary public school teachers' circumstances, which can open a new door for learning and research. Further qualitative study should be conducted to get the in-depth reason why teachers' self-concept towards dissatisfaction with their job is apparent.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The researcher wishes to convey his deepest gratitude and genuine appreciation to the following who contributed to the accomplishment of his work:

To the Almighty God, for the divine guidance that has illuminated throughout this academic endeavor; Dr. Eugenio S. Guhao Jr., DM, Dean of the Professional Schools and the researcher's advisor, whose expertise, encouragement, and unwavering commitment to academic excellence has been invaluable throughout the process. Dr. Guhao's guidance has been instrumental in shaping the direction of his research and refining the quality of this dissertation.

To Dr. Allan G. Farnazo, Regional Director, Region XI for allowing him to conduct this study in Davao Region together with the Superintendents; Dr. Raymunda L. Apostol, for her help, friendly concern, pieces of advice, and encouragement.

Members of the panel chaired by Dr. Mary Ann Tarusan, EdD for their views and ideas that helped improve this work and also, the researcher is grateful to his EdD classmates (Baganga and Cateel group) for the camaraderie, encouragement, and understanding during high and lows of this journey. Their help and presence have made this academic pursuit a more enriching and enjoyable experience.

He also wants to acknowledge the University of Mindanao community for providing a conducive and flexible academic environment and resources that were crucial to his research's success.

The researcher is profoundly thankful to his family for their unending support, understanding, and encouragement. Their love and belief have been the constant source of inspiration.

And lastly, he would like to express his gratitude to all those who played a role, directly and indirectly, in the completion of this dissertation. Their support has been a cornerstone of this academic achievement and the researcher is truly grateful for the collaborative spirit that has enriched his educational journey.

REFERENCES

- [1] Abiodullah, M., Sameen, D., Aslam, M. (2020). Emotional Intelligence as a Predictor of Teacher Engagement in Classroom. *Bulletin of Education and Research*, 42 (1), 127-140. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1258049.pdf>
- [2] Adolphs, R., Mlodinow, L., & Barrett, L. F. (2019). What is an emotion? *CB/Current Biology*, 29(20), R1060–R1064. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cub.2019.09.008>
- [3] Agyapong, B., Obuobi-Donkor, G., Burbach, L., & Wei, Y. (2022). Stress, Burnout, Anxiety and Depression among Teachers: A Scoping Review. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health/International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 19(17), 10706. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph191710706>
- [4] Ahn, J. H., & MyoungSuk, K. (2020). Effects of Emotional Intelligence, Self-leadership, and Critical Thinking Disposition on Clinical Reasoning Competence among Nursing Students. 27(3), 307–315. <https://doi.org/10.5953/JMJH.2020.27.3.307>
- [5] Allen, K., Slaten, C. D., Arslan, G., Roffey, S., Craig, H., & Vella-Brodrick, D. (2021). School Belonging: The importance of student and teacher relationships. In *Springer eBooks* (pp. 525–550). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-64537-3_21
- [6] Altikriti, S., Anderson, C. (2021). Factor Analysis and Structural Equation Modeling. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/343903164>
- [7] Amerstorfer, C. M., & Von Münster-Kistner, C. F. (2021). Student Perceptions of Academic Engagement and Student-Teacher Relationships in Problem-Based Learning. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 12. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2021.713057>
- [8] Amril, A., Ahyani, N., & Rahman, A. (2023). The managerial skills of principal and academic supervision on teacher's performance. *Journal of Social Work and Science Education*, 4(1), 251–260. <https://doi.org/10.52690/jswse.v4i1.375>
- [9] Atasoy, R., & Yalçın, M. T. (2023). *How school leadership affects teachers' professionalism via trust in administrator in bureaucratic school structures*. Digital Commons@NLU. <https://digitalcommons.nl.edu/ie/vol15/iss1/2/>
- [10] Atmaca, T. (2022). An Analysis of the Relationship among Teachers' Team Learning, Moral Commitment, and Career Commitment Using Structural Equation Modeling. *International Journal of Modern Education Studies*, 6(1). <https://doi.org/10.51383/ijonmes.2022.146>
- [11] Badarun, N., Rohmana, R., & Alberth, A. (2020). Emotional Intelligence and Students' Translation Ability at the English Department of Halu Oleo University. *Journal of Teaching of English*, 5(4), 318. <https://doi.org/10.36709/jte.v5i4.14056>
- [12] Barni, D., Danioni, F., & Benevene, P. (2019). Teachers' Self-Efficacy: The role of personal values and motivations for teaching. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 10. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2019.01645>

- [13] Batanero, J. M. F., Graván, P. R., Reyes-Rebollo, M. M., & Rueda, M. M. (2021). Impact of Educational Technology on Teacher stress and Anxiety: A literature review. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health/International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 18(2), 548. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph18020548>
- [14] Bay, D. (2020). Investigation of the relationship between self-efficacy belief and classroom management skills of preschool teachers with other variables. Retrieved from: <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1250487.pdf>
- [15] Bayawa, E.J.O., & Guhao, Jr., E.S. (2022). Mediating Effects of School Climate and Teachers' Personality on the Relationship between Principal Instructional Management and Teachers' Self-Efficacy among Elementary Teachers. *International Journal of Applied Science and Research*. 5(3), 122-164, May-June 2022.
- [16] Bong, M. & Skaalvik, E. M. (2003). Academic self-concept and self-efficacy: how different are they really? *Educ. Psychol. Rev.* 15, 1–40. doi: 10.1023/a:1021302408382
- [17] Bongcayat, J. T., & Guhao Jr, E. S. (2020). Structural equation model on work engagement of non-teaching personnel in public secondary schools. *Review of Integrative Business and Economics Research*, 9, 259-316.
- [18] Burić, I., & Kim, L. (2020). Teacher self-efficacy, instructional quality, and student motivational beliefs: An analysis using multilevel structural equation modeling. *Learning and Instruction*, 66, 101302. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.learninstruc.2019.101302>
- [19] Carby, N. (2023). *Structural leaders: the intersection of school principals, business leaders, and social networks*. ScholarWorks @ Georgia State University. https://scholarworks.gsu.edu/eps_diss/265/
- [20] Cherry, K. (2023). *5 key emotional intelligence skills*. Verywell Mind. <https://www.verywellmind.com/components-of-emotional-intelligence-2795438>
- [21] Cherry, K. (2023b). *Self efficacy and why believing in yourself matters*. Verywell Mind. <https://www.verywellmind.com/what-is-self-efficacy-2795954>
- [22] Daria, L. (2023). *Self-Efficacy, Self-Management and performance of teachers on the new normal*. <https://ejournals.ph/article.php?id=21357>
- [23] Ezzi, N. (2019). Teaching Performance in Relation to Emotional Intelligence among English Student-Teachers in the Teacher-Education Program in Hodeidah, Yemen. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/332042202_Teaching_Performance_in
- [24] Ferreira, M., Martinsone, B., & Talić, S. (2020). Promoting Sustainable Social Emotional Learning at School through Relationship-Centered Learning Environment, Teaching Methods and Formative Assessment. *Journal of Teacher Education for Sustainability*, 22(1), 21–36. <https://doi.org/10.2478/jtes-2020-0003>
- [25] Fishbach, A., & Woolley, K. (2022). The structure of intrinsic motivation. *Annual Review of Organizational Psychology and Organizational Behavior*, 9(1), 339–363. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-orgpsych-012420-091122>
- [26] Franklin, H., & Harrington, I. (2019). A Review into Effective Classroom Management and Strategies for Student Engagement: Teacher and Student Roles in Today's Classrooms. *Journal of Education and Training Studies*, 7(12), 1. <https://doi.org/10.11114/jets.v7i12.4491>
- [27] Gilar-Corbi, R., Pozo-Rico, T., Sanchez, B., & Castejon, J. L. (2019). Can emotional intelligence be improved? A randomized experimental study of a business-oriented EI training program for senior managers. *PLoS ONE*, 14(10). <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0224254>
- [28] GovPH (n.d.). *The Government*. Retrieved from <https://www.gov.ph/the-government/>
- [29] Guhao Jr, E. S. (2016). Conversational leadership of school heads and teacher sense of self-efficacy. *International Journal of Education and Research*, 4(11), 221-238.
- [30] Guhao Jr, E. S., & Quines, L. A. (2021) The mediating effect of authentic leadership of school heads on the relationship between teamwork attitudes and work engagement'. *International Journal of Business Management and Economic Review*, Vol. 4, No. 06; 2021. ISSN: 2581-4664.

- [31] H, Z., Yao, J., Zhang, Y., & Huang, X. (2023). The influence of teachers' intrinsic motivation on students' intrinsic motivation: The mediating role of teachers' motivating style and teacher-student relationships. *Psychology in the Schools*, 61(1), 272–286. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pits.23050>
- [32] Hen, M. (2020). Teaching Emotional Intelligence: an academic course for hospital teachers. *Continuity in Education*, 1(1), 22–36. <https://doi.org/10.5334/cie.13>
- [33] Hettinger, K., Lazarides, R., & Schiefele, U. (2023). Longitudinal relations between teacher self-efficacy and student motivation through matching characteristics of perceived teaching practice. *European Journal of Psychology of Education*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10212-023-00744-y>
- [34] Kaplan, D. (2000). *Structural Equation Modeling: Foundations and Extensions*. Sage, Newbury Park, CA
- [35] Karaköse, T., Kardas, A., Kanadlı, S., Tülübaş, T., & Yıldırım, B. (2024). How Collective Efficacy Mediates the Association between Principal Instructional Leadership and Teacher Self-Efficacy: Findings from a Meta-Analytic Structural Equation Modeling (MASEM) Study. *Behavioral Sciences*, 14(2), 85. <https://doi.org/10.3390/bs14020085>
- [36] Kaur, I., Shri, C., & Mital, K. M. (2019). The role of emotional intelligence competencies in effective teaching and teacher's performance in higher education. *Higher Education for the Future*, 6(2), 188–206. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2347631119840542>
- [37] Kelty, N. E., & Wakabayashi, T. (2020). Family engagement in schools: parent, educator, and community perspectives. *SAGE Open*, 10(4), 215824402097302. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2158244020973024>
- [38] Khassawneh, O., Mohammad, T., Ben-Abdallah, R., & Alabidi, S. (2022). The Relationship between Emotional Intelligence and Educators' Performance in Higher Education Sector. *Behavioral Sciences*, 12(12), 511. <https://doi.org/10.3390/bs12120511>
- [39] Khiat, H., & Vogel, S. (2022). A self-regulated learning management system: Enhancing performance, motivation and reflection in learning. *Journal of University Teaching & Learning Practice*, 19(2), 43–59. <https://doi.org/10.53761/1.19.2.4>
- [40] Kim, S., Raza, M., & Seidman, E. (2019). Improving 21st-century teaching skills: The key to effective 21st-century learners. *Research in Comparative and International Education*, 14(1), 99–117. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1745499919829214>
- [41] Lavy, S. (2022). A meaningful boost: effects of teachers' sense of meaning at work on their engagement, burnout, and stress. *AERA Open*, 8, 233285842210798. <https://doi.org/10.1177/23328584221079857>
- [42] Lenarz, K. (2020.). *Leadership preparation of preservice teachers*. Digital Commons @ Olivet. https://digitalcommons.olivet.edu/edd_diss/128/
- [43] Li, S. (2023). The effect of teacher self-efficacy, teacher resilience, and emotion regulation on teacher burnout: a mediation model. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 14. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2023.1185079>
- [44] Limos-Galay, J. A., Ferrer, J., & Genese, M. T. (2023). Effect of teaching performance on teachers' satisfaction in Rizal Elementary School. *International Journal of Research Studies in Management*, 11(12). <https://doi.org/10.5861/ijrsm.2023.1153>
- [45] Lu, Q., & Ishak, N. A. (2022). Teacher's Emotional Intelligence and Employee Brand-Based Equity: mediating role of teaching performance and teacher's Self-Efficacy. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.901019>
- [46] Lumbantobing, R. (2020). The Relationship Between Self-Concept and Emotional Intelligence. *Advances in Social Science, Education and Humanities Research*, 41. <https://doi.org/10.2991/assehr.k.200311.014>
- [47] Mahmud, M., Moonti, U., & Arifin, R. (2019). Impact of field experience on pedagogical competence of economic education students. *KnE Social Sciences*, 3(11), 495. <https://doi.org/10.18502/kss.v3i11.4029>
- [48] Maksimovic, J. Ž., & Osmanovic, J. S. (2019). *Teachers' Self-Concept and its Benefits for Science Education*. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ1315159>

- [49] Mamat, N. H., & Ismail, N. A. H. (2021). Integration of emotional intelligence in teaching practice among university teachers in higher education. *Malaysian Journal of Learning and Instruction*, 18(2), 69-102. <https://doi.org/10.32890/mjli2021.18.2.3>
- [50] Manla, V. H. (2021). School climate: Its impact on teachers' commitment and school performance. *Journal of World Englishes and Educational Practices*, 3(2), 21–35. <https://doi.org/10.32996/jweep.2021.3.2.3>
- [51] Martinsone, B., & Žydzūnaitė, V. (2023). Teachers' contributions to the school climate and using empathy at work: implications from qualitative research in two European countries. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 14. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2023.1160546>
- [52] Masoom, M. R. (2021). Educators' self-esteem: the effect of perceived occupational stress and the role of organizational support. *International Journal of Educational Management*, 35(5), 1000–1015. <https://doi.org/10.1108/ijem-11-2020-0550>
- [53] Masoom, M. R. (2021b). Teachers' Perception of Their Work Environment: Evidence from the Primary and Secondary Schools of Bangladesh. *Education Research International*, 2021, 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2021/4787558>
- [54] Meyers, S., Rowell, K. R., Wells, M. C., & Smith, B. C. (2019). Teacher empathy: A model of empathy for teaching for student success. *College Teaching*, 67(3), 160–168. <https://doi.org/10.1080/87567555.2019.1579699>
- [55] Miller, J. E. K. (2020). Teacher Effectiveness by Enhancing the Self-Concept and Interpersonal Relations: Strategies and Techniques. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, 10(1). <https://doi.org/10.30845/ijhss.v10n1a2>
- [56] Mitchell, M. (2019). *Teacher Self-Efficacy and Classroom Management*. ScholarWorks. <https://scholarworks.waldenu.edu/dissertations/7701/>
- [57] Mora-Ruano, J. G., Schurig, M., & Wittmann, E. (2021). Instructional leadership as a vehicle for teacher collaboration and student achievement. What the German PISA 2015 sample tells us. *Frontiers in Education*, 6. <https://doi.org/10.3389/educ.2021.582773>
- [58] Morin, A. (2021). *How Parents and Teachers Can Work Together for the Child's Benefit*. Verywell Family. <https://www.verywellfamily.com/parents-and-teachers-working-together-620922>
- [59] Munna, A. S., & Kalam, A. (2021). Teaching and learning process to enhance teaching effectiveness: literature review. *IJHI (International Journal of Humanities and Innovation)*, 4(1), 1–4. <https://doi.org/10.33750/ijhi.v4i1.102>
- [60] Mustafina, R.F., Ilina, M.S., Shcherbakova, I.A. (2020). Emotions and their Effect on Learning. *Utopía Y Praxis Latinoamericana*, 25(1), 318-324. <https://produccioncientificaluz.org/index.php/utopia/article/view/33708>
- [61] Nguyen, O. T. H. (2023). *The influence of principals' interpersonal communication skills on teachers' job satisfaction and job performance: A mixed method study*. Animo Repository. https://animorepository.dlsu.edu.ph/etdm_elmd/26/
- [62] Orakçı, Ş., Göksu, D. Y., & Karagöz, Ş. (2023). A mixed methods study of the teachers' self-efficacy views and their ability to improve self-efficacy beliefs during teaching. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.1035829>
- [63] Orğan, F., Kiss, J., & Simuţ, R. (2021). Self-Efficacy, Job Satisfaction and Teacher Well-Being in the K-12 educational system. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health/International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 18(23), 12763. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph182312763>
- [64] Özcan, M. (2021). Factors Affecting Students' Academic Achievement according to the Teachers' Opinion. *Education Reform Journal*, 6(1), 1–18. <https://doi.org/10.22596/erj2021.06.01.1.18>
- [65] Özdemir, G., Sahin, S., & Öztürk, N. (2020). *Teachers' Self-Efficacy Perceptions in terms of school principal's instructional leadership behaviours*. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ1244970>
- [66] Ponsades, O.P. & Guhao Jr., E.S. (2021). The Mediating Roles of Organizational Commitment and Organizational Climate on the Relationship between Principal Leadership and Work Wellbeing. *International Journal of Applied Science and Research*. 4(5), 140-192.

- [67] Pyhältö, K., Pietarinen, J., Haverinen, K., Tikkanen, L., & Soini, T. (2020). Teacher burnout profiles and proactive strategies. *European Journal of Psychology of Education*, 36(1), 219–242. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10212-020-00465-6>
- [68] Qin, Y. (2022). What part does instructional leadership play in making schools effective? *clausiuspress.com*. <https://doi.org/10.23977/aetp.2022.061013>
- [69] Rahmawati, D. (2021). Self-Efficacy, Teacher Leadership and Teacher Professionalism in Secondary School. <https://doi.org/10.25217/ji.v6i2.1190.1331>
- [70] Rodrigues, H. P. C., & De Lima, J. Á. (2021). Instructional leadership and student achievement: school leaders' perspectives. *International Journal of Leadership in Education*, 27(2), 360–384. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13603124.2020.1869312>
- [71] Saloviita, T., & Pakarinen, E. (2021). Teacher burnout explained: Teacher-, student-, and organisation-level variables. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 97, 103221. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2020.103221>
- [72] Samfira, E. M., & Paş, R. (2021). Teachers' personality, perfectionism, and Self-Efficacy as predictors for coping strategies based on personal resources. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 12. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2021.751930>
- [73] Savalei V., (2021). Improving Fit Indices in Structural Equation Modeling with Categorical Data. *Multivariate Behav Res.* 56(3):390-407. doi: 10.1080/00273171.2020.1717922. Epub 2020 Feb 13. PMID: 32054327.
- [74] Shaukat, M., Amir, R. M., & Raza, H. A. (2021). *Analysis of factors affecting motivation of teachers towards teaching; A case study of Public Schools Samanabad, Faisalabad*. <https://ajmesc.com/index.php/ajmesc/article/view/119>
- [75] Shen, J., Wu, H., Reeves, P., Zheng, Y., Ryan, L., & Anderson, D. (2020). The association between teacher leadership and student achievement: A meta-analysis. *Educational Research Review*, 31, 100357. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.edurev.2020.100357>
- [76] Shu, K. (2022). Teachers' Commitment and Self-Efficacy as Predictors of Work Engagement and Well-Being. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.850204>
- [77] Siriparp, T., Buasuwan, P., & Nanthachai, S. (2022). *The effects of principal instructional leadership, collective teacher efficacy and teacher role on teacher self-efficacy: A moderated mediation examination*. <https://so04.tci-thaijo.org/index.php/kjss/article/view/258493>
- [78] Song, X., & Ke, J. (2022). Job satisfaction, organizational commitment and turnover intention of university teachers in China's Pearl River Delta. *Advances in Social Science, Education and Humanities Research/Advances in Social Science, Education and Humanities Research*. <https://doi.org/10.2991/assehr.k.220504.297>
- [79] Songcog, J. M., & Guhao, E. S. (2020). A Structural Equation Model on Job Satisfaction among Non-Teaching Personnel in Private Higher Education Institution in Region XII, Philippines.
- [80] Srivastava, M., & Jaiswal, S. (2022). Emotional quotient vs. intelligence quotient to achieve professional excellence in life: a systematic literature review. *International Journal of Community Medicine and Public Health/International Journal of Community Medicine and Public Health*, 9(12), 4662. <https://doi.org/10.18203/2394-6040.ijcmph.20223229>
- [81] Su, H., Zhang, J., Xie, M., & Zhao, M. (2022). The relationship between teachers' emotional intelligence and teaching for creativity: The mediating role of working engagement. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.1014905>
- [82] Sumatra, J.M.T. (2021). Emotional Intelligence and Job Performance of the Teaching Employees at University of Bohol, Tagbilaran City. *Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 9(1). <https://universityofbohol.edu.ph/journals/index.php?journal=ubmrj&page=article&op=view&path%5B%5D=135>
- [83] Supramaniam, S., & Singaravelloo, K. (2020). Impact of emotional intelligence on organisational performance: an analysis in the Malaysian Public Administration. *Administrative Sciences*, 11(3), 76. <https://doi.org/10.3390/admsci11030076>

- [84] Thomas, J., Utley, J., Hong, S., Korkmaz, H., & Nugent, G. (2020). Parent involvement and its influence on children's STEM learning. In *Routledge eBooks* (pp. 323–333). <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780429021381-30>
- [85] Thurmond, T. (2023). Want to solve the teacher shortage? Start with increasing salaries. *EdSource*. <https://edsources.org/2023/want-to-solve-the-teacher-shortage-start-with-increasing-salaries/701802>
- [86] Turner, K., & Thielking, M. (2019). How Teachers Find Meaning in their Work and Effects on their Pedagogical Practice. *Australian Journal of Teacher Education*, 44(9), 70–88. <https://doi.org/10.14221/ajte.2019v44n9.5>
- [87] Ugoani, J. N. N., Amu, C. U., & Kalu, E. O. (2015). Dimensions of Emotional Intelligence and Transformational Leadership: A Correlation Analysis. *Independent Journal of Management & Production*, 6(2). <https://doi.org/10.14807/ijmp.v6i2.278>.
- [88] Ulfa, U., Zainal, A., Mayasari, R., Karim, N., & Rezki, A. (2022). The Relationship Between Self-Concept, Interpersonal Communication and Self-Adjustment in Students. Retrieved from <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3685-816X>
- [89] Usman, Y. D., & Madudili, C. G. (2019). *Evaluation of the effect of learning environment on students' academic performance in Nigeria*. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=ED602097>
- [90] Valente, S., Lourenço, A. A., & Domínguez-Lara, S. (2022). Teachers in the 21st Century: Emotional intelligence skills make the difference. In *IntechOpen eBooks*. <https://doi.org/10.5772/intechopen.103082>
- [91] Van Der Wal, L. (2020). *Parent-Teacher relationships and the effect on student success*. NWCommons. https://nwcommons.nwciowa.edu/education_masters/247/
- [92] van Dinther, M., Dochy, F., & Segers, M. (2011). Factors affecting students' self-efficacy in higher education. In *Educational Research Review* (Vol. 6, Issue 2, pp. 95–108). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.edurev.2010.10.003>
- [93] Ventista, O. M., & Brown, C. (2023). Teachers' professional learning and its impact on students' learning outcomes: Findings from a systematic review. *Social Sciences & Humanities Open*, 8(1), 100565. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssaho.2023.100565>
- [94] Verma, R. (2023). Does emotional intelligence make you an effective teacher? A study of higher education institutions. *American Journal of Education and Technology*, 2(4), 24–29. <https://doi.org/10.54536/ajet.v2i4.2108>
- [95] Winn, C. S., Cothorn, T. L., Lastrapes, R., & Orange, A. (2021). *Teacher Self-Efficacy and Principal Leadership Behaviors*. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ1328648>
- [96] Woo, H., LeTendre, G., Byun, S., & Schussler, D. (2022). *Teacher leadership -- collective actions, Decision-Making and Well-Being*. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ1342978>
- [97] Xie, F., & Derakhshan, A. (2021). A Conceptual review of positive teacher interpersonal communication behaviors in the instructional context. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 12. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2021.708490>
- [98] Yeung, A. S., Craven, R. G., & Kaur, G. (2014). *Teachers' self-concept and valuing of learning: relations with teaching approaches and beliefs about students*. *Asia-Pacific Journal of Teacher Education*, 42(3), 305–320.
- [99] Yu, X., Wang, X., Zheng, H., Zhen, X., Shao, M., Wang, H., & Zhou, X. (2023). Academic achievement is more closely associated with student-peer relationships than with student-parent relationships or student-teacher relationships. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 14. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2023.1012701>
- [100] Zandvliet, D. B., den Brok, P., Mainhard, T., Tartwijk, J. V. (2014). *Interpersonal relationships in education: from theory to practice*. Sense Publishers.
- [101] Zhou, Y. (2019). Collective Teacher Efficacy: an introduction to its theoretical constructs, impact, and formation. *International Dialogues on Education: Past and Present*, 6(2), 69-82. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ1245215>